

Space for local food production project report 2022

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Acknowledgements

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Executive summary

The Space for Local Production project aimed to support farmers to be part of a vibrant, prosperous, and diverse sustainable food economy for Monmouthshire. The project explored how to i) improve sustainability of farm businesses ii) develop future agricultural opportunities and, iii) adapt to climate and economic challenges.

The publication of the Welsh Government's outline proposals for the Sustainable Farming Scheme (SFS) has put the assessment of on-farm sustainability at the top of the agenda for Welsh farming. The work presented here trials such an assessment and assesses the challenges — and potential solutions — around engaging farmers on sustainability and driving change.

The outcomes of the project are related to four broad project objectives:

1. Support farms and land-based production to adapt to climate and economic challenges and develop future agricultural opportunities.
2. Support ecological resilience for community wellbeing.
3. Mapping/collation of data, tackling the climate and nature emergency through sustainable food and farming processes.
4. Upskill land based, agricultural and community producers/processors to help develop a vibrant, prosperous, and diverse sustainable food economy.

ADVISOR SURVEY

A survey of farm advisors in Wales addressed objectives 1 and 2 by i) exploring their perspectives on how they and the farmers they work with view sustainability ii) identifying barriers to engaging with farmers on sustainability and iii) highlighting potential solutions to tackle these barriers. The survey was distributed via Farming Connect to 88 farm advisors in Wales, and 43 completed responses were returned.

Survey responses suggested that farm advisors are currently less likely to give advice and/or information on social sustainability than on environmental sustainability. Different topics within social and environmental sustainability (such as community engagement, biodiversity, or nutrient management) received relatively even coverage in terms of engagement, demonstrating that advisors speak to their farmers on a broad range of issues. Respondents felt they were more likely to find it easy to talk to farmers on environmental sustainability topics than on social sustainability topics.

The majority of advisors responding to the survey felt that both social and environmental sustainability are important or essential to good farming practice. However, they expressed the view that both types of sustainability are only likely to be central to farming practice on some or a few of the farms they visit.

Almost half the advisors responding said that they did not feel that sustainability presented a different challenge to advisors than issues of economics and

Engagement in sustainability carries costs and encounters barriers which must be addressed before lasting change can be achieved.

productivity. For this group, analysis of their comments suggested that a holistic and discursive approach was part of their general practice when engaging with farmers. They had positive views about farmers' attitudes and focus on sustainability. Advisors who viewed sustainability as a different type of engagement challenge to topics relating to economics and productivity, felt that farmers were mainly focused on profit and not necessarily interested in sustainability.

Based on the analysis, it seems that some advisors have a professional approach which is focussed on the particular requirements of engaging on economics and productivity. This focussed approach can mean they are more challenged when providing advice around sustainability. A more holistic and discursive approach to farm advice in general may facilitate engagement on sustainability. Both viewpoints may be shaped by the types of farmers the advisors engage with, as much as by their own approach.

Fourteen challenge themes to engaging with farmers on sustainability were identified by advisors responding to the survey. Most of these challenges could be grouped into four categories: practical limitations, knowledge limitations, cognitive limitations, and interests. Two additional themes were i) advisor knowledge, experience, and perspective and ii) external communication (the context of engagement, shaped by messaging from policymakers, the media, and other groups).

These findings align with previously identified challenges to the implementation of climate friendly farming practices in Wales. They show that similar challenges affect both engagement with farmers on sustainability, and the implementation of change itself. This highlights that engagement carries costs and encounters barriers which must be addressed before lasting change can be achieved.

ADVISOR WORKSHOP

A farm advisor workshop examined: i) the relevance of sustainability assessments to tackling barriers to engagement faced by farm advisors, ii) barriers to the success of sustainability assessments and iii) the characteristics of an 'ideal' assessment from an advisor's perspective. These activities addressed objective 3. The workshop was held in Bulth Wells in February 2022 and attended by 10 advisors.

In the workshop, it was felt that a sustainability assessment could have a positive effect on several

A holistic, conceptual sustainability framework can be a low-cost way to reduce barriers to sustainability engagement and assessment.

engagement barriers (the knowledge and understanding of sustainability among farmers, the knowledge and understanding of farm advisors, and the complexity of sustainability). An assessment was felt unlikely to positively affect barriers relating to costs, financial pressures, or fear of external interference.

Advisors felt that a large group of barriers to engagement might, or would only partially, be addressed by an assessment — these were barriers associated with communication, trust, lack of agency, lack of clear benefits and difficulty of change. There were also mixed views on the impacts of an assessment on farmer mindset. While these challenges might be addressed by a well-designed assessment applied at the right time in a farmer's sustainability journey, there was concern an assessment with weaknesses applied at the wrong time could have a negative impact on these barriers to engagement and change.

Therefore, how assessments are designed, presented, and implemented is vital in determining their effect on the majority of challenges to engagement and change. To be successful in driving positive change, farm advisors felt that a formal sustainability assessment, like that provided by the GFM research tool, must be effective (clear, relevant and provide pathways to change), practical (usable and addressing issues of feasibility, applicability, and scope), and legitimate (transparent and robust).

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These required characteristics for an assessment fitted with solutions put forward in relation to knowledge and cognition-related barriers to engagement (i.e., the barriers which the advisors felt an assessment would most help to address). Solutions to address these barriers related to the context of engagement (supportive regulation and incentives, education and advisor training, and effective communication about sustainability), initial engagement (clarifying sustainability and highlighting the value of action for the farmer and for society) and creating a pathway to change (relevant and actionable information and learning from others).

Putting these findings together, highlights a tension between the role of sustainability assessments as a resource which can help solve knowledge and cognition-related barriers to change, and the barriers which such an assessment can create and exacerbate if they are not effective, legitimate, and practical.

This tension can be resolved by separating two aspects of any assessment: i) the use of a conceptual framework for understanding farm sustainability and, ii) a formal on farm assessment. It is the latter which runs the risk of facing barriers to engagement or even exacerbating them. In contrast, a holistic concept of sustainability presented separately from an assessment can be a low-cost way to reduce barriers to sustainability engagement.

The knowledge, understanding, and ideas that could be generated by farmers discussing a holistic sustainability framework with advisors and peers, would leave farmers much better placed to undertake a formal assessment and to make use of the findings. This would better enable them to use assessment results to drive change benefitting their business, the environment, and the wider community.

TRIAL RESULTS

Objectives 3 and 4 were addressed by the trialling of the Global Farm Metric framework and research tool with 10–20 farmers in the Monmouthshire area, and through the collection of feedback from farmers and advisors involved in the trial.

The Global Farm Metric research tool results aim to enable farmers to consider farm sustainability across economic, social, and environmental categories. This provides an overview of strengths and areas for improvement, widens perspectives on

what sustainability includes, and as a result should reduce the chances that decisions made on-farm will cause unintended consequences for many often-overlooked aspects of sustainability.

The individual and group summary results received by farmers should provide a starting point for them to consider how to improve their system, including in discussion with their peers, with their workers, with advisors, and with other stakeholders as appropriate. Repeating such an assessment over time can help to track progress and to spot any trade-offs (or ‘win-wins’) which were not previously recognised.

For the Monmouthshire farmers involved in this trial, the best category results (top five) were in animal husbandry, crop and plant health, human, productivity, and soil. The lowest five scoring categories were water, nutrient management, energy and resource use, social, and biodiversity. These five areas may be seen as priorities for improvement, while variation in scores within the group offer opportunities for learning between high and low scoring farms in particular categories.

In addition to their individual farm results and a group summary, farmers were given the chance to attend a discussion session at the Four Salmons Hotel in Usk in September 2022. They also received reports from the Wye and Usk Foundation with suggestions on how they could improve sustainability on their farms. This step from assessment results to supporting farmers to identify concrete pathways to change is a vital component of any sustainability assessment process.

All models and assessments have limitations, and barriers to implementing change are multiple and vary with context. Therefore, it is important for any findings from quantitative assessments or modelling

The results provide a starting point to consider farm improvements and enrich discussions. Repeated over time, progress and trade-offs can be monitored.

to be the start of processes of reflection, discussion, and change, rather than being viewed as the end of the thinking process.

TRIAL FEEDBACK

The most important challenge associated with the Global Farm Metric research tool from the perspective of farmers and farm advisors, was practical – the time taken to complete the assessment. Concerns included how this could particularly disadvantage older farmers, those with fewer IT skills, and those with more complex production systems which require the farmer to input more data.

Derived from the work in this project and consideration of the issues, solutions around the time taken to complete the assessment include i) improved design to minimise data requested and to align required information with that requested by other tools and assessments, ii) working towards simpler, more intuitive assessment design, iii) carrying out the assessment at less busy periods (for these farmers, winter), iv) providing support for data collection and entry (in the form of advisors or through the use of other people or automated techniques to collect data) and, v) ensuring the relevance of the assessment to farmers — this might be through alignment with policy or through actions to improve farmer understanding of why such assessments (and sustainability itself) are important to their practice and to the wider community.

A second issue was the intention for the assessment to be repeated annually. While the value of benchmarking over time was recognised by farmers, they emphasised that changes in many of the variables measured would take place relatively slowly, so that re-assessment every 2–5 years would be most likely to demonstrate improvements.

Further challenges related to the perceived robustness of the tool, with farm advisors highlighting that data collection methods which seem unreliable can undermine the willingness of farmers to persevere with any assessment — in this case a drought affected worm counts and the soil infiltration test was found to give highly variable results.

Assessment developers need to identify robust indicators and methods of data collection which provide results in the simplest way possible. This practicality must be balanced against the need to ensure that results are reliable and at a level of

Practical challenges highlight the need for accessible, robust and supported assessment.

detail which recognises positive aspects of a farm (e.g., the quality of hedgerows for wildlife, not just their length). Reducing the amount and detail of financial information required was also felt to be important — providing data on finances is (understandably) a particularly sensitive issue in relation to farmer trust.

Positively, farmers involved in the trial i) gained new insights relating to farm sustainability, ii) developed new ideas for change and iii) reported an increased likelihood that they would make improvements as a result of the assessment. The advisors involved also felt that they had gained new understanding of farm sustainability.

Considering the views of farmers before and after the assessment, the holistic view of on-farm sustainability appeared to highlight for farmers the potential trade-offs between production / profit and sustainability. This holistic awareness can be beneficial to change and reduce unintended or unexpected consequences. However, the interpretation of results needs to provide pathways to change which include ‘win-win’ social-economic-environmental changes that demonstrate that the farm business and sustainability are not always in opposition. In the short-term, pressures to increase yields can create tensions around sustainability actions which may reduce production, but the goal of achieving long-term sustainability in food production aligns much more with the need for actions to increase resilience through environmental improvement. Farmers were very aware of the need to ensure food supply for future generations, highlighting the potential to align farming and environmental interests around long-term goals.

Key messages

Barriers to farmer engagement

The Space for Local Production project demonstrates that previously recognised barriers to transition towards more sustainable farming practices, are also challenges to engaging with farmers on sustainability.

Power of holistic frameworks

Holistic frameworks for understanding farm sustainability have the potential to reduce knowledge- and cognition-related barriers to engagement, providing clarity and demonstrating the value of change to farmers and wider society.

Foundation before assessment

For many farmers, the use of a holistic framework like the Global Farm Metric to increase understanding of farm sustainability is required before formal sustainability assessments are attempted — otherwise such assessments can increase the barriers to future engagement and fail to drive change.

Assessment tool potential and limits

Experience with the Global Farm Metric research tool demonstrates that a formal assessment which is transparent, robust, practical to use, designed for simple data entry, provides information relevant to the farmer, and provides pathways for change, can help farmers think differently about sustainability, discover opportunities for improvement, and avoid making decisions that have unintended consequences for sustainability. However, limitations to the current tool (and to similar assessments) in terms of the time taken to collect and input data, make it difficult to apply without a high level of external support. Solving these issues is essential before sustainability assessments are rolled out more widely.

Insights through the process

Trial feedback showed that the process of undertaking the Global Farm Metric assessment (not just its results) can provide farmers with insights into farm sustainability, stimulate new ideas and thinking around opportunities for change, and lead to farmers feeling they are more likely to implement such ideas.

Support turns insight into action

Farmer and advisor feedback showed that providing concrete advice and support to interpret assessment results and convert them into actions on farm, particularly through collective processes in which farmers learn from each other's experiences, is central to ensuring that a sustainability assessment has a positive real-world impact.

Sustainability requires shared responsibility

Lasting change requires real buy-in from farmers but also from other stakeholders who contribute to the sustainability issues affecting the farming community — from industries generating greenhouse gas emissions that threaten crop yields and animal health, fly-tippers polluting the on-farm environment, and developments that have an impact on farmland biodiversity, reductions in rural services, and the low prices paid for farm produce by large buyers. Sustainability assessments should be a first step in identifying the different organisations and individuals who need to act (along with the farmer) to improve the state of farming systems affected by both on-farm and off-farm activities.

Change needs collective action

This research has shown that change towards more sustainable farming at the scale required to address global warming, biodiversity loss, and global food supply challenges will require processes, not just assessments, support, not just instruction, and collective efforts, not just individual action by farmers.

Next steps

Key areas for action in Monmouthshire are identified, with next steps including improved decision-making and collaboration. The Global Farm Metric looks to improve its practical application, time-efficiency and usefulness for farmers and advisors, as well as supporting wider tool refinement and alignment.

The findings presented here are being used by the Global Farm Metric team to:

- Develop the Global Farm Metric framework as a knowledge resource for farm advisors and farmers, and as a basis for learning materials for higher education and courses for teachers and agricultural sector professionals.
- Support the alignment of data requirements across tools and assessments, enabling farmers to reduce duplication of effort when providing data
- Explore latest developments and improvements in data collection methods for sustainability assessment (including using remote sensing, automated monitoring, and inputs from volunteers)
- Update the tools used in Global Farm Metric trials to reduce the time requirement for farmers through improved indicators, design, data collection requirements, and data collection methods.

The Global Farm Metric results gathered, and the learning gained by all involved in the project provide insights which can underpin and focus actions to increase the sustainability and resilience of farming in Monmouthshire, and to enable farmers to communicate more of their sustainability story to their customers.

This work highlights that further actions in Monmouthshire centred on farm nutrient management, water, energy and resource use, biodiversity and community engagement are likely to enhance aspects of sustainability which were (on average) lower scoring in this trial than other sustainability categories, and that processes in which farmers and other stakeholders can work together to achieve change could be particularly effective. In relation to biodiversity in particular, exploration of the use of satellite data to reduce farmer workload and build new insights into sustainability assessment would also be valuable.

1. Introduction

The Space for Local Production project was funded under the UK Community Renewal Fund. This fund supports pilot programmes and tests new approaches to support local economic growth, prior to the introduction of the UK Shared Prosperity Fund.

The UK Community Renewal Fund invests in projects that cover one or more of the investment priorities of skills, community and place, local business, and supporting people into employment. In Great Britain the fund is managed in partnership with local authorities who act as Lead Authority for their area.

The project was part of wider action to develop the Monmouthshire Food Resilience programme and local supply chains, to build public awareness and an active food citizenship, and to pilot community action to target food insecurity. It aimed to support farmers to be part of a vibrant, prosperous, and diverse sustainable food economy for Monmouthshire. The project explored how to: i) improve sustainability of the farm business, ii) develop future agricultural opportunities, iii) adapt to climate and economic challenges.

In the light of the publication of the Welsh Government's outline proposals for the Sustainable Farming Scheme the work of this project has gained extra significance in considering challenges to engaging Welsh farmers on sustainability and in trialling a holistic on-farm sustainability assessment.

The overall project objectives were to:

1. Support farms and land-based production to adapt to climate and economic challenges and develop future agricultural opportunities.
2. Support ecological resilience for community wellbeing
3. Mapping/collation of data, tackling the climate and nature emergency through sustainable food and farming processes
4. Upskill land based, agricultural and community

producers/processors to help develop a vibrant, prosperous, and diverse sustainable food economy

The activities undertaken, the objectives they address, and the reasoning behind them are summarised in Table 1. Together these activities aimed to define pathways for change towards increased sustainability on Monmouthshire farms and in Welsh agriculture more broadly, identifying and exploring the role and potential of sustainability assessment in this process and trialling the implementation of such an assessment. They are divided into three parts in this report: farm advisor views; on-farm trials; farmer and farm advisor trial feedback.

In this report the terms 'farm advisor' and 'farm consultant' are used interchangeably to refer to anyone providing knowledge or advice to farmers — in Wales such knowledge exchange may be offered free (e.g., via government funding), paid for by farmers, or offered in connection with the sale of farm inputs.

Table 1: Project activities, relevant objectives, and reasoning

Activity	Objective	Reasoning
Understand farm advisor perspectives on how they and the farmers they work with view sustainability — including whether they feel sustainability present unique challenges to farm knowledge exchange	1, 2	To support improved sustainability and resilience in the context of climate, ecological and economic challenges, farmers must engage with the topic and be guided by advisors equipped to support them along pathways of change. A pre-requisite to achieving this, is to understand how advisors view sustainability and how they feel about engaging with farmers on related topics
Identify barriers to engaging with farmers on sustainability from the perspective of farm advisors, and discuss potential solutions	1, 2	Change also requires specific barriers to engaging with farmers on sustainability to be tackled and, to achieve this, those barriers and potential solutions must be identified
Consider the relevance of sustainability assessments to tackling barriers to engagement and change faced by farm advisors	3	For an assessment to fulfil its purpose of collecting data to drive change, it must be taken up by farmers. Understanding whether an assessment could break down barriers to engagement, or whether it would be likely to require preparatory work to bring farmers into the process is therefore vital
Identify challenges to the success of sustainability assessments and the characteristics of an 'ideal' assessment from the perspective of farm advisors	3	An assessment must make a good impression with farmers if it is to engage them and drive change; determining the characteristics of an 'ideal' assessment and the challenges an assessment might face from the perspective of farm advisors is therefore important to the development of all sustainability assessments
Trial the Global Farm Metric framework and assessment tool with 10–20 farmers in the Monmouthshire area to gain an overview of their current sustainability performance across economic, social, and environmental categories.	3, 4	Sustainability assessments directly collect data on the sustainability performance of farms and, in doing so, provide producers with an overview of their farm in relation to economic, social, and environmental sustainability, giving them the knowledge to explore ways to improve, change, and take advantage of, opportunities around sustainability
Collect feedback from farmers undertaking the trial (and the farm advisors supporting them) to examine: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How the assessment affected their views on sustainability and the likelihood that they would seek to improve sustainability performance 2. How the process of the trial worked for them, and what might be improved 3. Their feelings about the results and the performance of the assessment tool itself 	1, 2, 3, 4	Understanding how farmers and farm advisors experienced the GFM sustainability assessment will support the future design and development of the GFM framework, the GFM research tool and other tools designed to address these topics. It will enable us to better support farmers to switch towards more sustainable farming systems, from initial engagement through to assessment, changes in practice and improved sustainability outcomes.

2. Farm advisor views

This section outlines project activities focused on farm advisors' views on sustainability and its role in knowledge exchange. It explores how they and the farmers they support perceive sustainability, the barriers to engagement, and possible solutions. It also considers how sustainability assessments can help address these barriers and what makes an effective assessment. Outcomes are summarised in Table 1.

2.1. APPROACH

The first part of the work with farm advisors in Wales gathered information by questionnaire on how they and the farmers they work with viewed sustainability. This included whether they felt sustainability presented unique challenges to farm knowledge exchange — and asked them to identify barriers to engaging with farmers on sustainability. The survey included a mix of multiple choice and open text questions (Appendix A). It was created in Google Forms and distributed by Farming Connect via email to 88 farm advisors in Wales, from an estimated population of around 200 farm advisors in the country (FC, pers comm).

Open text responses, as well as solutions and discussions from the workshop, were analysed using a grounded theory approach (Bryant & Charmaz, 2012): Individual comments, challenges, solutions etc. (according to the exercise being analysed) were coded to reflect their content and gathered into themes, rather than being fitted into a pre-existing classification (Ritchie et al., 2014). The themes relating to challenges, solutions, issues for sustainability assessment, and the assessment wish list, as well as discussions about how an assessment could affect different barriers to engagement, were all extracted from the data using this method. Responses to multiple choice questions were charted and (where relevant) differences in response frequencies explored using Chi-squared tests with a null hypothesis of equal response numbers for all options.

The survey sections on challenges to engaging with farmers, and the workshop session on solutions

described below, were based around the 'Future' workshop approach (Jungk & Müllert, 1987) in which challenges are defined in relation to a particular topic, as well as the ideal world to be aimed for. Solutions to reach it are then put forward by the group. Here, the research team defined the ideal world as 'achieving engagement by farmers on sustainability' and challenges were identified from survey responses.

The second part of the work gathered the views of farm advisors attending a workshop arranged by Farming Connect and held on February 15th in Builth Wells. All 88 farm advisors contacted for the survey were invited to this event, and ten attended. The workshop focussed on identifying solutions to the barriers to engaging with farmers on sustainability identified in the survey, asked participants about the relevance of sustainability assessments to tackling barriers to engagement and change, and considered challenges to the success of such assessments and the characteristics of an 'ideal' assessment from their perspective.

Engagement in sustainability carries costs and encounters barriers which must be addressed before lasting change can be achieved.

In the first workshop session, participants were introduced to the aims of the project and specifically to the work with farm advisors. The challenge themes revealed from survey responses were described to the whole group. Following this, the group was divided into two, with a facilitator and notetaker for each sub-group. Discussions within each sub-group were recorded by Dictaphone and later transcribed for analysis. Challenge themes from analysis of the survey were written up on a flip chart for each group and discussed to ensure that their meaning was clear, and to allow participants to add new challenges they felt were missing. For each challenge, participants were asked to write potential solutions on sticky notes (one note for each individual solution) and the solutions were discussed.

In the second session, participants were presented with a broad overview of the GFM tool sustainability assessment, as an example of the types of assessment being focused on. In the two sub-groups, the advisors were asked to use coloured dots to vote on the extent to which they believed a sustainability assessment could address the different challenges to engaging with farmers on sustainability (identified in the survey and discussed in the morning session).

They were asked to think about sustainability assessments in general but had been given access to materials and a presentation on the Global Farm Metric in advance, as an example of what such assessments can cover. After voting, participants then discussed the score given to each by the group.

Next, participants were asked to identify challenges to the use of a sustainability assessment on-farm. As for the voting, an assessment in this case was defined broadly as a framework for considering sustainability (the Global Farm Metric categories and sub-categories) and the use of a tool to collect data and return indicators of sustainability for the farm.

Discussions were framed to encourage participants to think about challenges for sustainability assessments in general, rather than to focus on specific technical limitations with the GFM tool used within the SE Wales trial — this was to ensure that the ideas shared would be relevant to any sustainability assessment, rather than simply critiquing the GFM framework and tool. Challenges were written on sticky notes and then discussed by the group. Having discussed these challenges, the process was repeated but this time to create a wish-list for an ideal sustainability assessment.

2.2. FINDINGS

The results of the analysis of survey responses are described below in relation to specific topics.

2.2.1. VIEWS ON SUSTAINABILITY

Initial multiple-choice questions indicated that, of the advisors surveyed, more provide information on environmental sustainability to farmers than on social (Fig. 1a, b). In relation to environmental sustainability, the topic which the fewest advisors reported covering was plant and crop health; other topics were covered relatively evenly, with air pollution covered the least (16 responses) and greenhouse gas emissions the most (26). The least covered topic in social sustainability was employment conditions (9) and the most sharing skills and experiences (23).

Fig. 1: The topics within environmental (a) and social (b) sustainability currently discussed with farmers by farm advisors responding to the survey.

These findings highlight that farm advisors in Wales are engaging with farmers across a wide range of issues. The high coverage of greenhouse gas emissions could be explained by the current policy focus on global warming. The low coverage of plant and crop health probably reflects the dominance of the livestock sector in Welsh agriculture. For topics within social sustainability, looking at employment conditions may not be considered as a role for farm consultancy. Farm structure, training and capacity building, and sharing skills and knowledge are much more established focuses for farm engagement.

When asked about their feelings on the importance of environmental and social sustainability for good farming practice, most advisors reported feeling that both were essential (Fig. 2a, b). However, for social sustainability a bigger proportion of responses fell into the ‘important but not essential’ and ‘positive but not important’ categories, with one response indicating that social sustainability was ‘negative for good farming practice’.

Fig. 2: How important farm advisors felt that environmental (a) and social (b) sustainability were for good farming practice.

Despite positivity in the feelings of surveyed advisors about the importance of social and environmental sustainability, these findings indicate that social sustainability is not as highly valued in relation to farming practice as environmental sustainability. This may reflect the fact that farming directly and practically relies on the state of the environment, and vice versa, while social impacts of farming (positive or negative) may be related to practice but not so directly, and with more obvious potential for conflict (e.g., between farming practices and public access, or profitability and workers' wages).

The largest number of respondents believed that, for the farmers they interact with, both environmental and social sustainability were central to farming practices on some or a few farms (Fig. 3a, b). For social sustainability the highest number of responses was in the category 'on a few farms'.

Fig. 3: Responses to the question: For how many of the farms you interact with, is environmental (a) or social sustainability (b) currently central to farming practices

The responses to this question highlight that despite apparent recognition among farm advisors of the importance of environmental and (to a lesser extent) social sustainability, advisors do not feel that this recognition is shared by the majority of the farmers they interact with. This shows there is still work to be done to engage many Welsh farmers with the concept of sustainability, which may be seen as a pre-requisite to them seeking to make changes to improve their farms' environmental and social performance.

Responding on whether they would find it easy to engage with the farmers they work with on sustainability, the highest response rates around environmental sustainability were in the categories '[easy with] all farmers' and '[easy with] most farmers', while for social sustainability the highest number of responses were for '[easy with] most farmers' and '[easy with] some farmers' (Fig. 4a, b).

The pattern of responses shows that advisors feel that engagement on environmental sustainability is likely to be easier on more farms than engagement on social sustainability, and that for many, sustainability is likely to be a difficult topic on at least some of the farms they visit. Again, this emphasizes the work that remains to be done to bring farmers on-board with the sustainability agenda.

Fig. 4: Responses to the question: With how many of the farmers you engage with would you / do you find it easy to talk about improving environmental (a) or social (b) sustainability

2.2.2. IS SUSTAINABILITY A NEW CHALLENGE FOR FARM ADVISORS?

Previous research has shown that the challenges for knowledge exchange related to climate friendly farming may be different to those for knowledge exchange on other topics (Kipling & Becoña, 2019). Therefore, the survey tested the assumption that the challenges to engaging with farmers on environmental and social sustainability (considered together) would be different from the challenges to engaging on farm economics or productivity (more traditional topics for farm knowledge exchange). Of the 40 responses to this question, 22 thought that the challenges were different, three were unsure but 15 did not think that engaging on sustainability posed different challenges versus engaging on farm economics or productivity. Thus, the assumption tested did not hold for 37.5% of respondents.

Analysis of the open text comments giving respondents' reasons for their answers, revealed differences in the reasoning of advisors who agreed versus those who did not agree that sustainability engagement posed different challenges to engagement on economics or productivity (Fig. 5).

The theme 'attitude of farmer' was common to both 'yes' (there is a difference between engagement on environmental/social sustainability and engagement on economics or productivity) and 'no' (no difference) responses and related to the viewpoint and focus of farmers. However, for the yes group, farmers were considered more used to and comfortable with talking about economics and productivity than about sustainability and were focused on the former issues. In contrast, for the 'no' group farmers are viewed as having a long-term perspective, with many already understanding and taking action on sustainability.

The theme 'linkage' was also common to both groups, but again the emphasis differed between the 'yes' and 'no' groups. The 'yes' group focused on the need to link discussions of sustainability to economic or production related benefits to farmers. For the 'no' group, the emphasis was on the interrelatedness of the whole farming system and the fact that individual aspects such as the environment or production could not be considered in isolation.

The final two themes differed between the two groups. For the 'yes' group, the nature of sustainability as a topic — being less black and white and more nuanced — posed challenges to

engagement. For the 'no' group, the approach of the advisor formed the third theme, with emphasis on how the positivity and passion of the approach to farmers can enable positive discussion on sustainability.

The analysis of the reasons for advisors thinking that engagement on sustainability did or did not pose different challenges for engagement than farm economics or productivity, suggests that advisors who take a holistic approach to their practice with farmers are able to apply this approach to questions of sustainability just as to other questions, while that those who have focused in their practice on the particular requirements of engagement on economics and productivity may need to alter their approach and thinking when talking to farmers about sustainability.

Further work is needed to understand the extent to which the differences in perspective and approach between 'yes' and 'no' groups of advisors reflected differences in the farmers they engage with, versus being the result of differences in the advisors' approach affecting farmer responses. However, the findings described indicate that i) a holistic approach to farm systems by advisors, in which economics and productivity are discussed alongside environmental and social sustainability, as well as ii) clear and positive advisor buy-in to the need for and opportunities of sustainability, are key elements of successful engagement with farmers on environmental and social sustainability.

2.2.3. CHALLENGES TO ENGAGEMENT ON SUSTAINABILITY

The advisor survey identified fourteen challenges to engagement with farmers on sustainability (Fig. 6) which mapped onto general categories of barrier to change in Welsh farming identified in an earlier study (Kipling et al., 2019a). Recent work on barriers to farmers engaging in agri-environment schemes also revealed issues which mapped onto the same general categories, while in addition this work highlighted the role of farm characteristics, farmer age and farmer disabilities as indicators of increased barriers to engagement (Hurley et al., 2022). Two challenge themes in the current study related to issues beyond the farm: external communication and advisor knowledge, experience, and perspective. A brief description of each challenge theme was created (Table 2).

FIG. 5: Themes (bold text) emerging from analysis of the reasons given by farm advisors for answering 'yes' or 'no' to the question 'Do you think the challenges of engaging farmers on environmental/social sustainability are/would be different to the challenges to engaging them on farm economics or productivity?' Sentences in quotes are examples of respondents' comments making up each theme for 'yes' and 'no' respondents. Grey arrow shows themes which differed between respondent groups (see main text for details).

FIG. 6: Challenges to engagement with farmers on sustainability mapped onto the four categories of challenge identified by Kipling et al. (2019a) (practical, knowledge, cognitive, interests) as key barriers to change towards more climate friendly farming practices in Welsh livestock farming, plus the additional category 'Communication and advisory issues'. Asterisk denotes one challenge which was revealed during the second workshop session (as a result, it was not included when participants voted on the extent to which a sustainability assessment could address the challenges).

TABLE 2: DESCRIPTIONS OF CHALLENGES TO ENGAGEMENT WITH FARMERS ON SUSTAINABILITY IDENTIFIED BY FARM ADVISORS

Theme title (and category)	Theme description	Example comments
External communication	How mixed and sometimes conflicting information about sustainability in the media and from policymakers can lead to people holding a range of views about what the term means. Unclear communication from media and policymakers can affect how other parts of society view farming, and in turn affect the mindset of farmers, who may become more cautious or negative about engaging on sustainability.	<p>“The biggest problem is the way that the messages are put across and that farming seems to have become secondary to land management – they are intrinsically linked.”</p> <p>“Sustainability is not clearly defined and means different things to different people.”</p>
Advisor knowledge, experience, and perspective	Advisors’ own knowledge limitations about aspects of social and environmental sustainability and issues associated with engaging farmers on sustainability, in terms of the farmers’ reaction or of the complex and sometimes controversial nature of the topic itself. An important aspect of this challenge is that advisors (and farmers) can lack information / data on sustainability — this can lead to big assumptions being made about what it means and the options for improvement.	<p>“I am not knowledgeable to talk in a very informed way [on social sustainability]”</p> <p>“It’s difficult to promote something which isn’t physical or easily quantifiable.”</p>
Distrust of sustainability agenda (Interest)	Farmers may feel wary of talking about the environment, perceiving that people are trying to catch them out as a result of press coverage and a changing public discourse that has moved away from farming (external communication). This is associated with distrust of evidence showing the benefits of environmental sustainability, and of the motives of those advocating for it.	<p>“The anti-farming brigade and negative press means most farmers are wary or talking about environment as they often feel someone is trying to trip them up or be negative about their business.”</p> <p>“There can be a wariness about ‘environmental do-gooders.’”</p>
Fear of external interference (Interest)	farmers may fear increased regulation and potential sanctions if they engage on sustainability, with interference in their business if they open up as well as concerns about public access to farms and farmland.	<p>“Fear of official interference and un-controlled public access.”</p> <p>“Interference in their businessby people who don’t understand practical farming!”</p>

Theme title (and category)	Theme description	Example comments
Mindset of farmer (Interest)	<p>Whether farmers see sustainability as a priority for the farm — especially in relation to social sustainability. In some cases, farmers might even be attached to practices that reduce the success of their business — these practices might have to be dealt with first to put them in a position where they are able to engage on sustainability. Other farmers may be generally resistant to change in what they are doing, and it was suggested that the age of the farmer can be a factor in relation to adopting more sustainable practices. Especially in relation to social sustainability, personality is also important — many may be introverts and/or value their privacy when it comes to inviting people onto the farm.</p> <p>Financial motivation, time, and costs were mentioned at the same time as many responses relating to mindset, indicating the blurred line between not wanting to and not being able to change and suggesting links to the perceived complexity of sustainability, and distrust of the sustainability agenda. Some responses spoke about farmers fearing for the future or discussing retirement, and therefore being hard to engage on sustainability.</p>	<p>“...it can be difficult at times to persuade farmers that there are other options available.</p> <p>“Many farmers are private and what to keep things to themselves and their families.” [in relation to social sustainability and public access/ events]</p> <p>“Depends on the age and capability of the farmer to understand, their priorities and interests – those who are more business/performance minded being easier to engage.”</p>
Poor community-farmer relations (Interest)	How farmers engage with their community can affect the extent to which local concern about sustainability can be a driver of change, and the extent to which having positive social effects in the local area matters to a farmer. Poor relationships with the local community can therefore reduce the scope for engagement on sustainability, while good relations can open opportunities for change.	<p>“As soon as you’ve got a reputation as a good guy it’s great, but if you get a reputation as a bad guy it’s very hard to win it back.”</p> <p>“There’s been good examples of people giving up pieces of land for allotments hasn’t there? I mean they’re charging a rent for them but at least the public have got an allotment.”</p>

Theme title (and category)	Theme description	Example comments
Farmer knowledge (Knowledge limits)	Some farmers lack knowledge/education on sustainability and, at another level, farmers who know about sustainability and want to change, but don't know what their options are. Underlying these problems, a lack of a sustainability ethos and narrative in farming education and training was identified as an issue	<p>"There is a serious issue of a 'little bit of knowledge is dangerous' concerning sustainability and farming communities, big assumptions are made."</p> <p>"The main problem is that farming college/university courses are funded by an industry that doesn't have sustainability at its core and that such issues are barely covered and therefore seen as peripheral to many farmers."</p> <p>"A greater problem is ignorance of what can be done i.e. those farms that want to develop more sustainable practices but do not have the personal knowledge of what they can do or where to go for technical support."</p>
Farmers' understanding (Cognitive limits)	Focused on whether farmers understood the risks of not changing, the importance of sustainability or how it fits into the bigger picture.	<p>"Depends on the age and capability of the farmer to understand."</p> <p>"[issue of] actually appreciating that it [social sustainability] is part of the overall picture."</p>
Lack of agency (Cognitive limits)	Farmers may feel that in a global context, changes they make as individuals will not make a difference — they might need practical examples of changes they can make to address this. In addition, farmers may not always have (or feel they have) the opportunities to undertake actions to improve social or environmental sustainability.	<p>"[Farmers asking] 'What difference will my small farm make?'"</p> <p>"Farmers quite often don't have the opportunities for engaging in these [social sustainability related] activities."</p>
Benefits unclear (Cognitive limits)	Farmers often lack a clear idea of the potential benefit to them of improving farm sustainability. This included being clear on (and quantifying) potential financial benefits from improved practices, from increased value of products to consumers and from potential policy incentives which are currently uncertain. Therefore, the theme has links to external communication as it arises from poor definition of what sustainability involves and implies for farmers.	<p>"Proving the worth of doing something and incorporating it into their general farm practice."</p> <p>"Lack of clear policy objectives and incentives."</p>
Complexity of sustainability (Cognitive limits)	As sustainability isn't easily quantifiable and has many aspects, it is hard to communicate on one hand, and on the other farmers can feel overwhelmed by its scope — they need time to take everything in before deciding what to do.	<p>"[Farmers have] so many things to do in relation to environmental sustainability that they are overwhelmed with where to start."</p> <p>"Requires a different perspective and time to consider the issues."</p>

Theme title (and category)	Theme description	Example comments
Short-term financial pressures (Practical limits)	farms are often struggling just to survive, and don't have money to invest in things that only have long term benefits or improve environmental or social sustainability without financial benefit.	<p>"For those that are financially constrained they are not in a position to invest now for a long-term benefit."</p> <p>"...reduced resource, negative returns, increasing costs..."</p>
Difficulty of change (Practical limits)	farmers may feel that changes may be hard to incorporate into their practices or systems or that they may not have the right skills. The theme was small and closely linked to 'costs of change' — it could be viewed as a non-financial aspect of the costs of change, which is potentially important as it indicates that addressing financial challenges might not be sufficient to enable farmers to improve their practices.	<p>"Sustainability approaches can require more work and greater investment."</p> <p>"Everyone would like to do it, but for some the cost of change or the structure of their business currently makes it too difficult or financially uneconomical to make significant changes."</p>
Cost of change (Practical limits)	Financial and time costs of making changes. In relation to social sustainability, costs discussed were mainly in terms of farmers' time, possibly because things like school visits and public access were considered not to involve much investment. Therefore, although aspects of social sustainability (e.g., paying higher wages) could have financial cost implications, these were not raised in the responses. In relation to environmental sustainability, the financial costs of making changes and also the ongoing costs associated with continuing with the changes over time were mentioned. Impacts on output were highlighted separately, suggesting that this is an issue in itself (even if profits are not affected by change) for some farmers. Finally, in some cases advisors said that sustainability just wasn't discussed, as other priorities dominate farmers' time — even engaging has a cost.	<p>"If it impacts on output levels, they [farmers] are wary"</p> <p>"Effect on profit especially when they are going to lose their Basic Payment Scheme money"</p>

2.2.3.1. SYTHESIS OF CHALLENGES TO ENGAGING WITH FAMRERS ON SUSTAINABILITY

The challenges put forward by advisors demonstrate the difficulty of communicating on a complex topic with a range of aspects that is hard for individual advisors to gain expertise in, and with unclear benefits for the farmer — particularly in the context of often confusing or negative messaging from the media or the policy world. The latter can add distrust and sometimes fear to farmers’ caution around the topic of sustainability, affecting the farmers’ mindsets in a range of ways. Alongside and interacting with these issues of motivation or perspective, are issues of farmer knowledge and understanding in the context of ongoing financial pressures on farm businesses — which means they have little time to consider new aspects of farming while struggling to keep afloat. These challenges can affect the extent to which farmers feel able to make meaningful change, even if they want to.

Connected to all of these, the costs of change — in terms of time and resources — were identified as important barriers to change — from the time taken to even engage on the topics, to the costs associated with implementing change and then maintaining altered practices.

The practical difficulties of change were mentioned but less emphasized than the costs — engaging farmers on sustainability represents a distinct task, taken a step before more detailed examination of options for change, at which point such practical difficulties could be expected to come more to the fore.

Although the knowledge, experience and perspectives of advisors were challenges raised in relation to engaging farmers on sustainability, for the most part responses focused on the outlook and barriers associated with farmers themselves, or with the wider context of engagement. However, issues such as the complexity of sustainability, and the lack of clarity around benefits for change, might also be viewed as limitations to be addressed by advisors.

Previous work on communication of climate change modelling highlighted the divide in perception associated with challenges of communication, in that the responsibility for failure can be placed on either side. For example, is the modeller communicating mathematical ideas unclearly, or is the level of mathematical knowledge in the population too low? (Kipling & Özkan Gülzari, 2016).

The challenges which advisors face to engaging with farmers on sustainability reflect the fact that, for many in the agricultural industry, considering long term environmental, economic, and social sustainability requires a change in perspective (while recognising that some farmers and advisors already consider farming in a holistic way — see above) to look beyond short-term maximisation of production in their practices. Altering this perspective requires farmers to have the breathing space from short-term financial and practical pressures: struggling to meet a range of demands under pressure in relation to input costs and outputs prices, many farmers have little time to reconstruct their viewpoint and strategy to a more sustainable approach, and even if they could, would need to then find the resources and undertake the training to implement it.

The importance of the research undertaken by Hurley et al (2022) is to highlight that the context of the farming system and the characteristics of the farmer affect the size of the barriers to engagement and change identified.

2.2.4. THE ROLE OF A SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT

What role might a sustainability assessment have in tackling these barriers to engagement on sustainability? With some challenges grouped together to ensure the process was manageable, farm advisors at the workshops indicated whether an assessment would definitely help to tackle each challenge, would not help, or was uncertain to help. The responses (Fig. 7) show a mixed picture: for most challenges the highest number of farm advisors voting were uncertain about the effect of an assessment; for two most were positive, and for another two most were negative. Discussions about these votes took place in both workshop groups and are summarised in Table 3.

FIG. 7: Farm advisor views on whether a sustainability assessment would help them to tackle challenges to engagement with farmers on sustainability: orange = will not help, grey = unsure if would help / would partially help, green = will help. This differed between respondent groups (see main text for details).

TABLE 3: DESCRIPTIONS OF HOW FARM ADVISORS FELT A SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT COULD HELP TACKLE EACH CHALLENGE TO ENGAGEMENT.

Challenge title	Summary of discussion	Example comments
Fear of external interference	One perspective was that a sustainability assessment could be seen as a part of external interference, or as something that could lead to external interference — if this is a barrier to engaging on sustainability at all, it will also be a barrier to taking the further step of assessing sustainability. Establishing trust in the assessment would be important to the success of an assessment. Fear of engaging with the public was an additional aspect of this challenge theme which arose in discussions, particularly in relation to social sustainability. An assessment might help reduce this fear by giving farmers knowledge and understanding of sustainability and on their own performance — this could boost their confidence and willingness to engage on these topics and reduce their fear of facing questions they can't deal with. However, farmers may still lack the skills or not have a personality conducive to public engagement. Overall, the voting suggested that fear of external interference might be increased by the suggestion of a sustainability assessment, rather than decreased. There was some positivity about how an assessment might support farmers to engage with the public, but this was an indirect benefit associated with increased farmer knowledge and understanding, discussed below.	<p>“And I think as well they think someone’s going to come onto the farm, they’re going to give us advice how to do things — it’s going to cost us money, it’s going to cause us more problems in the long run — maybe they can’t — I guess that goes back to their mindset, whether they see it as a positive to move them forward or whether it’s a negative”</p> <p>“I suppose if it’s all well enough publicised and trusted before it gets started perhaps that will make a big difference.”</p> <p>“It might help them to be better informed to engage with the public and give them a bit of confidence I suppose — they’re more educated so they won’t fear that as much”</p>

Challenge title	Summary of discussion	Example comments
Cost of change / Short term financial pressure	Participants highlighted the fact that an assessment in itself couldn't tackle the issue of needing money to implement changes on farm (including to fund carrying out the assessment), although over time it was recognised that farmers could track their costs as they changed practice and find ways to become more sustainable without losing out financially.	<p>“Who’s going to fund all these changes — is the farmer going to get £5000 a year for going through all this?”</p> <p>“First time around it doesn’t do much, but I was assuming this is going to be a regular thing, so this is where we are at the start, this is where we are in year one, this is where we are in year two, this is where we are in year three — I would expect costs and finances to come out of that because that’s going to be a really powerful determination of whether they’re going to do it or not.”</p>
Difficulty of change	An assessment that shows different categories or aspects in which change can be achieved can break down an overwhelming set of goals into something manageable step by step — working category by category can also build confidence and show change. In contrast, if the issues raised cannot be tackled, this can be very negative in terms of empowering people to make changes.	<p>“It might well be that there needs to be some focus on what things you concentrate on first, because it’s soul destroying to answer questions and then there are no solutions for it”</p> <p>“If you start on a process where you think, oh right I can do something about one or two of them [aspects of sustainability], and then maybe when you get there, you think ‘oh, you know what, that wasn’t so bad, I can do number two now”</p>
Distrust of environmental sustainability agenda	Participants felt that clarity about what sustainability meant was important to trust. Validating the benefits of an assessment beforehand could help build trust. Overall, gaining trust was not only a matter of ensuring an assessment was effective — if the process was not handled well a loss of trust could undermine engagement in sustainability as a whole.	<p>“It could go either way, couldn’t it? If you do it the right way you could build trust, if you do it the wrong way you could totally blow it before you get started”</p> <p>“I think you’d have to validate its value beforehand. This works (tried and tested) — you’d have to absolutely have to nail that first for them to become engaged.”</p>

Challenge title	Summary of discussion	Example comments
Lack of agency	<p>Participants felt that clarity about what sustainability meant was important to trust. Validating the benefits of an assessment beforehand could help build trust. Overall, gaining trust was not only a matter of ensuring an assessment was effective — if the process was not handled well a loss of trust could undermine engagement in sustainability as a whole.</p> <p>The focus of discussion was around the social aspect of a holistic assessment, with a view that asking farmers to deal with environmental sustainability and at the same time to understand and make changes on social aspects would be confusing and potentially reduce interest in sustainability as a whole. Farmers might lack the opportunities to involve themselves in some aspects of social sustainability, like hosting education visits.</p>	<p>“If I’ve done all the pure environmental stuff first, and I get that and I’m in tune with it, then I would be much more receptive to the community and wider societal benefits from it. But instinctively I would not want to do them both together. I think it would really confuse, and I think it would disengage people”</p>
Effective communication	<p>Participants did not put forward any reasons for the scoring of this challenge further, perhaps because it underlies many of the other challenges (engagement being primarily a matter of communication) or perhaps because it was seen as clear that if something is not well and clearly communicated, this will be a barrier to engagement. However, clarity of communication arose specifically in the discussion of the challenge ‘distrust of the sustainability agenda’</p>	
Benefits unclear	<p>Responses in the discussion of this challenge overlapped with the discussion on farm costs and financial pressures, focusing on the fact that only applying an assessment over time would start to demonstrate financial impacts, with one view being that an assessment which doesn’t put its findings in monetary terms can’t address this challenge.</p>	<p>“Initially I don’t think it’s going to help that much, but on the basis that it becomes a regular thing, which they choose to do or have to do then I would expect costs and finances to come out of it.”</p> <p>“The assessment doesn’t put any pound signs against things — it doesn’t help you to understand what the implications might be for costs and finances”</p>

Challenge title	Summary of discussion	Example comments
Mindset of farmer	<p>There was not much discussion of this challenge as how it would be affected by an assessment was seen to depend on the farmer’s starting position. Some might react positively to an assessment, some negatively. This insight demonstrates the importance of tailoring knowledge exchange approaches to the context of the individual farm, and highlights the importance of the skill and experience of the farm advisor in judging the approach likely to work best with particular farmers.</p>	<p>“The range of the mindset of the farmers goes from one end of the spectrum to the other. We’re all different aren’t we?”</p>
Complexity of sustainability	<p>Participants discussed how assessment can form a structured whole, which both allows farmers to see sustainability in overview, avoiding single issue approaches and unintended consequences (whole) and, by defining the parts that make up that whole, enables them to identify understandable ways forward in that context (structured). In this way, the complexity of sustainability is made clear while its parts are also clarified — understanding of complexity can be achieved at the same time as practical solutions can be identified. This double role is aided by visual presentation in which everything can be taken in. When associated with actions such as data collection, the visual, holistic aspects means that the farmer knows what is going to be covered (rather than e.g., putting in data bit by bit without knowing how much more there is, or trying to keep up with a range of different initiatives without knowing how they fit together, or where the gaps are).</p>	<p>“I think it just shows the linkage and integration of what you’ve got to do — that’s when the total becomes greater than the sum of its parts.”</p> <p>“It might show the complexity of change — isn’t that a good thing, to show it isn’t all about one track you might go down. It’s quite positive in educating the farmers: ‘it is difficult and you need to appreciate it is difficult.’”</p> <p>“I think a pictorial approach is actually quite good to see, rather than a linear, word-based approach”</p>

Challenge title	Summary of discussion	Example comments
Advisor knowledge, experience, and perspective	If the assessment is robust, particularly in terms of goals based on good data and benchmarking that ensures farms with different characteristics are not unfairly compared, then participants believed it would help advisors gain a better view of best practice solutions. However, to address specific aspects of a holistic assessment and to understand it correctly in specific contexts will require advisors who have knowledge and experience of that context and those aspects. So, the assessment can build advisor knowledge, but finding sensible options for the farmer in the light of that assessment needs advisors to already have a good understanding of the system and of the sustainability aspects in question.	<p>“So long as it’s the right person [advisor] in the right slot because you could easily, having the wrong person in that slot, have a bit of a disaster”</p> <p>“— if you’re comparing like with like — if it’s not directly transferable and you can’t get some sort of normal mean data to validate it, then I think it’s going to be a problem.”</p>
Farmer knowledge and understanding	One perspective was that the amount to be communicated in a holistic sustainability assessment could be overwhelming, while the opposite view was that just seeing the scope of the issue, built understanding in itself — actually going through the process of an assessment was also recognised as something that could build knowledge and understanding. Ensuring relevance to the farmers’ context was raised as one aspect of effectively building knowledge and understanding.	<p>“I thought — there’s a lot in there — species, breeds, soil”</p> <p>“Even if they just see the [Global Farm Metric] wheel, there’s 11 categories — so they see the wheel, 11 categories, OK, wouldn’t have thought about that one, you’re actually starting to nudge up their level of understanding.”</p> <p>“If you go through the process — they’ve got to engage so it means they’re suited to it. By going through it, it can’t help but improve their understanding.”</p>

Challenge title	Summary of discussion	Example comments
Farmer knowledge and understanding – skills	In relation to farmer knowledge and understanding, farm advisors went on to think about how a sustainability assessment could affect farmers’ skills — level of skill is more likely to be a barrier to implementing change on-farm than to engaging with sustainability — however, farmer skills might increase a farmers’ sense of agency (the feeling that their actions matter and that they are empowered to do what they would like to). Comments on farmers skills included a discussion about whether negative findings could put people off developing their skills — it was felt by some that this was a matter of mindset and that poor performance could be seen as an opportunity for change, while a holistic assessment should show positives in some aspects, which can provide encouragement. Taking things step by step was again raised as a way to make an assessment more likely to be effective in driving change and the role of benchmarking in motivating farmers to help each other was highlighted.	<p>“But that [poor performance in everything] means you can only get better — if you’re at the top you can only go downhill. It depends on your mindset.”</p> <p>“I think it points them in the right direction doesn’t it, potentially? It points out the limits doesn’t it — you’re no good at soil management, go and do this — will it not help with that sort of thing?”</p> <p>“But I would find it unlikely that any farmer would go through it and they would be bad at everything...You’d think they’d be good at some, bad at others and they’d have something to work on wouldn’t you?”</p>

2.2.4.1. SYTHESIS OF THE ROLE OF SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENTS

The descriptions and discussions of challenges to engaging with farmers and the potential for sustainability assessments to tackle them, reveal that the barriers to engagement are also likely to be barriers to actual change. Barriers to change can contribute to or reflect the challenges for engagement — for example, if a farmer does not have time to engage, they are unlikely to have time to make a change. On the other hand, if they feel improving sustainability is not in their interest, they are unlikely to feel it worthwhile engaging with a farm advisor on how to make such improvements.

As a result, initial engagement not only needs to tackle challenges that prevent farmers engaging but, to be most effective, must also include information that addresses the barriers to change themselves — for example, by defining concrete, effective actions they can take to alter practical limitations. This is necessary to avoid these underlying barriers to change cutting short discussions with advisors, even when specific barriers to engagement have been addressed.

2.2.5. SOLUTIONS TO THE CHALLENGES TO ENGAGING WITH FARMERS ON SUSTAINABILITY

This section examines the solutions that farm advisors put forward in the workshop to address the challenges to engagement with farmers on sustainability. It focuses on the solutions put forward relating to the top three challenges that advisor votes suggested a sustainability assessment would be likely to improve (see Fig. 7), i.e., farmer knowledge and understanding; advisor knowledge, perspective and experience, and complexity of sustainability.

Seven solutions themes were identified from analysis of the discussions on ways to tackle these three challenges to engagement on sustainability (Table 4).

TABLE 4: SOLUTIONS TO KNOWLEDGE AND COGNITION RELATED CHALLENGES TO SUSTAINABILITY ENGAGEMENT (THOSE WHICH SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT WAS FELT TO BE DEFINITELY ABLE TO TACKLE).

Solution themes	Theme Descriptions	Example comments
Regulation and incentives	These were suggestions of how regulations and law could be used to drive change by making practices illegal or obligatory: for example, regulating pesticide use by requiring prescriptions, or requiring basic qualifications for farm advisors. It also included the use of incentives to get farmers and advisors to undertake learning or to persuade farmers to directly improve performance, while emphasising the need to get rid of incentives that rewarded poor productivity. What started out as a discussion of solutions to challenges of engagement, merged into a discussion of challenges to change itself — highlighting how the two types of barrier interweave.	<p>“Pesticides only to be used by prescription”</p> <p>“Make certain actions by farmers obligatory for receiving subsidies”</p> <p>“Mandate [farmers] to learn about key issues / get qualifications – link to inheritance tax or rewards”</p> <p>“Maybe CPD (Continuous Professional Development) points [like] ROSA (Register of Sheep Advisors) — wider appreciation of sustainable farming”</p>
Education and advisor training:	Comments relating to this theme highlighted the need for education around sustainability across all levels from primary school upwards, and the need for that education to go beyond the farm to consider the wider impacts of farming practice. The importance of having high standards of expertise amongst advisors was also raised. Comments emphasized that the breadth of sustainability meant that a single advisor would be unlikely to be able to provide the needed support to farmers across all areas — specialist advisors for different sustainability topics and specific farm types were viewed as important.	<p>Long term strategy in education required — messages all through education from primary school — balanced view important”</p> <p>“Education — not just about the farm but much wider global impact — conscience — social — impact on others / wildlife / biodiversity”</p> <p>“Information and training is required — industry specific”</p> <p>“Training — broader appreciation of wider impacts of advice — but hard to be expert in everything”</p> <p>“Specialist advisors for topics”</p>
Effective communication (expressed as a solution, versus its lack as a challenge)	Communication was considered important to engagement on sustainability at all levels, including from the farming press, from policy makers and from advisors. Messaging needs to be aligned, jargon-free and clear.	<p>“Are policy makers, advisors and farmers aligned?”</p> <p>“Plain language delivery, no jargon”</p> <p>“Clear policies needed — legislation changing”</p>

Solution themes	Theme Descriptions	Example comments
Clarify the issue	The comments which make up this theme focus on the need to clarify basic terminology and the key goals of sustainability in order to enable farmers to understand the challenge, its relevance to them, and the ways they can address it. Breaking sustainability down into parts with practical relevance to farmers was considered important to this process. At the same time, farmers needed to understand sustainability holistically – the connectivity of its different aspects and how actions have wider impacts off farm, as well as the potential trade-offs and mutual benefits between aspects of sustainability on farm.	<p>“Where do I start? What is sustainable development?”</p> <p>“What is the extent of the problem / challenge – why do I have to do it?”</p> <p>“Break it down into bite-sized chunks and work towards some at a time at farm level – i.e., water, soil”</p> <p>“The total needs to be greater than the sum of its parts”</p> <p>“Need to know how an action impacts on all aspects of sustainability – e.g., feed soya to dairy cows – impacts on carbon, rainforest etc.”</p>
Highlight the value of action	The comments making up this theme focused on the need both to help farmers see how implementing change could positively affect them but also on helping them understand why change on a single farm is worthwhile given the scale of the problems.	<p>“What difference will my small farm make to be more sustainable?”</p> <p>“What’s in it for me?”</p> <p>“Showing farmers impacts [of their farming] elsewhere in the world”</p>
Learning from others	This theme was made up of comments relating to how both farmers and advisors can learn from examples and case studies of positive action and from sharing information in groups – benchmarking of performance was suggested as one part of this.	<p>“Farmers sharing information through groups of similar interests”</p> <p>“Benchmarking to give knowledge / learning from others, and so farmers follow others”</p> <p>“I had a good example of a dairy group in Herefordshire who were all benchmarking their businesses and the bottom one – they were sharing with each other and somebody came bottom – and the bottom one said ‘God, what do I do now?’ and the top two went and helped him. They actually helped him, they went to his farm, talked about the business – brilliant”</p>

Solution themes	Theme Descriptions	Example comments
Relevant and actionable information	These comments highlighted the importance of communicating information relevant to the farmer’s system, including by connecting the farmer to the advisor with the right area of expertise, with measurement of performance providing one way to help decide what type of advice would be of most use. The use of specialist advisors could also solve the issue of advisors having to know about so many different themes when giving advice on sustainability. The advice should also be relevant to actions, helping farmers identify the easiest, quickest or most important actions to take first, in particular when the farm has diverse enterprises needing different solutions. This includes prioritising the knowledge needs of farmers in different situations.	<p>“Connecting farmers to right advisor for a specific topic”</p> <p>“Industry specific information readily available”</p> <p>“What are the quick wins re improving sustainability”</p> <p>“Does everyone’s level of understanding need to be the same?”</p>

2.2.5.1. SYNTHESIS OF SOLUTIONS TO ASSESSMENT-RELEVANT CHALLENGES TO ENGAGEMENT

The solutions described can be presented in connection to one another (Fig. 8). Regulation and incentives for engagement, education and training for advisors and effective communication form the context for engaging with farmers. Clarifying the issue and highlighting the value of change then form the first step of engagement, with a focus on providing relevant and actionable information and opportunities for learning from others in order to drive change.

The solutions above focus not on the method of knowledge exchange delivery (like articles, videos, group advice, or sustainability assessment) but on the nature of the content involved. With one exception described below, methods for engagement on sustainability can be pragmatically chosen by the farm advisor from their toolkit to suit a particular farmer and context. However, if sustainability is not clearly defined, if the value of improving sustainability is not highlighted, and if information is not relevant or actionable, no method is likely to work.

The exception to the suggestion that methods of engagement may be chosen freely so long as the right content is involved, is that the solutions put forward by advisors suggest that not only should engagement on sustainability occur between advisor and farmer, but there should also be engagement between farmers on the topic. In other words, group approaches and/or the sharing of examples and case studies of good practice should be part of the mix.

FIG. 8: Farm advisor’s solutions to tackling knowledge and cognitive challenges to engaging with farmers on sustainability (the types of challenge felt most likely to be addressed by sustainability assessment)

2.2.5.2. EVALUATING THE SOLUTIONS

The solutions described and discussed by advisors can be considered using the framework developed by Kipling et al. (2019b) to understand the different ways that change can be approached in farming, and the potential implications of these different strategies. Each solution fits into the framework, which defines solutions according to whether they work around, overcome, or alter the four key barriers to change, and whether they represent a facilitative, controlling, or empowering approach to change (Fig. 9). In this case, the change being focused on is moving farmers towards engaging with farm advisors on sustainability — as described, the barriers to this change identified by farm advisors grouped into the four types of barriers in the framework (practical limitations, knowledge limitations, cognitive limitations, and interests).

Regulation and incentives

Regulation can overcome Practical limitations by forcing change, while incentives can overcome these limitations by providing resources. Regulation can alter Practical limitations by allowing particular solutions or by inhibiting actions which might have made them risky to implement

Both incentives and regulation can overcome Interests by compensating farmers for taking actions they would not otherwise take

Regulation or incentives used to Overcome the Interests of farmers is a **Controlling** approach. Regulation or incentives used to Overcome or Alter Practical limitations is **Empowering** if Interests are aligned with the change

Accommodate (market / farmers), Control (policy / market) or Empower (shared)			
Challenge	Work around	Overcome	Alter
Practical limitations	Cheap, low effort solutions; Solutions carried out by others	Provide resources to implement actions; regulate or prohibit	Reduce resource costs through new practical solutions or altered regulation
Knowledge limitations	Solutions not needing new knowledge; Solutions carried out by others	Provide precise protocols to be followed	Provide practical knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding
Cognitive limitations	Solutions not needing new understanding; Solutions carried out by others	Provide decision support systems; Solutions that simplify practice	Provide management knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding
Interests	Solutions aligned to interests; Solutions carried out by others	Regulate, prohibit, incentivise or persuade	Facilitate sharing of ideas and needs between groups

Education & consultant training

Education and consultant training Alters Knowledge limitations and Cognitive limitations in both increasing actual knowledge and the understanding of how it can be applied

Education and consultant training is an **Empowering** approach so long as it is genuine and not used to persuade instead of to inform

Accommodate (market / farmers), Control (policy / market) or Empower (shared)			
Challenge	Work around	Overcome	Alter
Practical limitations	Cheap, low effort solutions; Solutions carried out by others	Provide resources to implement actions; regulate or prohibit	Reduce resource costs through new practical solutions or altered regulation
Knowledge limitations	Solutions not needing new knowledge; Solutions carried out by others	Provide precise protocols to be followed	Provide practical knowledge and skills , chances to share understanding
Cognitive limitations	Solutions not needing new understanding; Solutions carried out by others	Provide decision support systems; Solutions that simplify practice	Provide management knowledge and skills , chances to share understanding
Interests	Solutions aligned to interests; Solutions carried out by others	Regulate, prohibit, incentivise or persuade	Facilitate sharing of ideas and needs between groups

Effective communication

Effective communication focused on informing can Alter Knowledge and Cognitive limitations by providing practical and management knowledge and skills and sharing understanding.

Effective communication focused on persuading can be used to Overcome Interests by 'selling' ideas in a partial way. However, if it seeks to share ideas and solutions between groups it can also Alter those Interests.

Effective communication can be **Empowering** when focused on Knowledge and Cognitive limitations, or when used to Alter Interests, but can be **Controlling** if used to persuade.

Accommodate (market / farmers), Control (policy / market) or Empower (shared)			
Challenge	Work around	Overcome	Alter
Practical limitations	Cheap, low effort solutions; Solutions carried out by others	Provide resources to implement actions; regulate or prohibit	Reduce resource costs through new practical solutions or altered regulation
Knowledge limitations	Solutions not needing new knowledge; Solutions carried out by others	Provide precise protocols to be followed	<u>Provide practical knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding</u>
Cognitive limitations	Solutions not needing new understanding; Solutions carried out by others	Provide decision support systems; Solutions that simplify practice	<u>Provide management knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding</u>
Interests	Solutions aligned to interests; Solutions carried out by others	Regulate, prohibit, incentivise or persuade	Facilitate sharing of ideas and needs between groups

Highlight value of action

Highlighting the value of action on sustainability can Alter Interests by demonstrating to farmers the positive effects of change (or the negative effects of inaction) on themselves and others, and that by their actions specifically they can make a real difference. This is achieved through Altering Knowledge limitations around the impacts of their actions.

Highlighting the value of action is **Empowering** so long as the knowledge shared aims to inform rather than to persuade using biased or intentionally incomplete information (in which case it could become **Controlling**), it can be **Accommodating** if it shows farmers that sustainability is aligned to their interests, without persuading them of this.

Accommodate (market / farmers), Control (policy / market) or Empower (shared)			
Challenge	Work around	Overcome	Alter
Practical limitations	Cheap, low effort solutions; Solutions carried out by others	Provide resources to implement actions; regulate or prohibit	Reduce resource costs through new practical solutions or altered regulation
Knowledge limitations	Solutions not needing new knowledge; Solutions carried out by others	Provide precise protocols to be followed	<u>Provide practical knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding</u>
Cognitive limitations	Solutions not needing new understanding; Solutions carried out by others	Provide decision support systems; Solutions that simplify practice	Provide management knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding
Interests	<u>Solutions aligned to interests</u> ; Solutions carried out by others	Regulate, prohibit, incentivise or persuade	<u>Facilitate sharing of ideas and needs between groups</u>

Clarify the issue

Clarification of an issue can Alter Cognitive limitations by helping farmers to conceptualise an issue simply and communicate it to others.

Clarification of an issue can also Alter Interests by enabling farmers to understand it more clearly and thereby come to a more informed view on whether they want to engage with it.

Clarifying an Issue is **Empowering** in relation to Cognitive limitations and Interests

Accommodate (market / farmers), Control (policy / market) or Empower (shared)			
Challenge	Work around	Overcome	Alter
Practical limitations	Cheap, low effort solutions; Solutions carried out by others	Provide resources to implement actions; regulate or prohibit	Reduce resource costs through new practical solutions or altered regulation
Knowledge limitations	Solutions not needing new knowledge; Solutions carried out by others	Provide precise protocols to be followed	Provide practical knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding
Cognitive limitations	Solutions not needing new understanding; Solutions carried out by others	Provide decision support systems; Solutions that simplify practice	<u>Provide management knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding</u>
Interests	Solutions aligned to interests; Solutions carried out by others	Regulate, prohibit, incentivise or persuade	<u>Facilitate sharing of ideas and needs between groups</u>

Learning from others

Learning from others can Alter Knowledge and Cognitive limitations or – if only very precise information or solutions are taken in without full understanding – they can be used to Overcome those limitations without Altering them.

Learning from others can also Alter Interests by adding to the understanding of those involved.

Learning from others is **Empowering** in relation to Interests and to Knowledge and Cognitive limitations, unless those being learned from are not attempting to persuade – in which case it could be **Controlling**.

Accommodate (market / farmers), Control (policy / market) or Empower (shared)			
Challenge	Work around	Overcome	Alter
Practical limitations	Cheap, low effort solutions; Solutions carried out by others	Provide resources to implement actions; regulate or prohibit	Reduce resource costs through new practical solutions or altered regulation
Knowledge limitations	Solutions not needing new knowledge; Solutions carried out by others	Provide precise protocols to be followed	<u>Provide practical knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding</u>
Cognitive limitations	Solutions not needing new understanding; Solutions carried out by others	Provide decision support systems; Solutions that simplify practice	<u>Provide management knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding</u>
Interests	Solutions aligned to interests; Solutions carried out by others	Regulate, prohibit, incentivise or persuade	<u>Facilitate sharing of ideas and needs between groups</u>

Relevant and actionable information				
Accommodate (market / farmers), Control (policy / market) or Empower (shared)				
Challenge	Work around	Overcome	Alter	
Practical limitations	Cheap, low effort solutions; Solutions carried out by others	Provide resources to implement actions; regulate or prohibit	Reduce resource costs through new practical solutions or altered regulation	
Knowledge limitations	Solutions not needing new knowledge; Solutions carried out by others	<u>Provide precise protocols to be followed</u>	<u>Provide practical knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding</u>	
Cognitive limitations	Solutions not needing new understanding; Solutions carried out by others	<u>Provide decision support systems; Solutions that simplify practice</u>	<u>Provide management knowledge and skills, chances to share understanding</u>	
Interests	Solutions aligned to interests; Solutions carried out by others	Regulate, prohibit, incentivise or <u>persuade</u>	<u>Facilitate sharing of ideas and needs between groups</u>	

Fig. 9: Assessing how the solutions to engaging with farmers on sustainability put forward by farm advisors fit into the Kipling et al. (2019b) framework, including brief explanations. General examples of potential options for change represented by each point in the matrix are shown and, for each engagement solution, the relevant mechanisms of change shown in black bold text and underlined: a) Regulation and incentives, b) Education and advisor training, c) Effective communication, d) Clarify the issue, e) Highlight value of action, f) Learning from others, g) Relevant and actionable information.

Regulation and incentives can get farmers to engage without really understanding or signing up to the logic of the issue or the need to take action — such interventions may bring change by force or persuasion, but it may not be effective or persist in the long term (Fig. 9a). A good level of education on sustainability amongst farmers and advisors, training of the latter to engage farmers on sustainability issues, and a context of clear and positive messaging from policy and the media can provide an enabling environment to engagement on sustainability (Fig. 9 b,c) Key to engaging with farmers is making clear what sustainability is, what it covers, why it is important and how change on farm can help improve things. A holistic view of sustainability which at the same time highlights individual components farmers can relate to and affect is important to achieving this (Fig. 9d,e). Once farmers are engaged with the issue and wish

to understand what changes they can make, the information and support provided must be relevant to their specific system and context and drive concrete actions. One way this can be achieved (which at the same time can show how individual actions can make a difference) is through learning from others through examples and case studies of changes made elsewhere — these examples can also help farm advisors to see how their colleagues have achieved change, and to see what types of actions are effective (Fig. 9 f,g). In the long run, altering barriers to change (rather than working around them or overcoming them) and achieving this by empowering those involved (rather than by just accommodating or controlling them) are the most robust strategies for achieving change. Reliance on control can be ineffective and have negative effects (Kipling et al., 2019b). How interventions are made to drive engagement and,

ultimately, change, matters. Accommodating existing limitations and interests can only bring small, gradual changes that work around issues. Controlling interventions which overcome or alter barriers may not be sustainable, as they do not bring stakeholders with them, but force or persuade them into changes — this can lead to high costs to maintain changes, inefficiency because stakeholder understanding is not brought to bear in identifying best practice, and a loss of human capital as stakeholders move from being professionals motivated to deliver into being automatons just following external directions. In contrast, empowering approaches deliver knowledge and understanding. They allow these to grow through interactions between stakeholders, so that farmers themselves appreciate the need for sustainability and apply themselves to deliver it. This should occur in the context of a supportive policy environment which alters the practical limitations on-farm and addresses potentially negative interventions from external groups, while maximising the positive roles of such groups.

2.2.6. SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENTS: WHAT IS NEEDED?

The work already described suggests that, for advisors, sustainability assessments as one of the methods in their toolkit, may or may not be the best way to engage particular farmers on sustainability — the key lies in the assessment’s characteristics or content. This was shown in Fig. 7, which demonstrated that the advisors involved in the workshop were unsure whether such an assessment could positively affect many challenges to engagement (and therefore to change) which they faced. Consequently, the next focus of this work was to consider the issues that a sustainability assessment needs to address, and the characteristics that make for an assessment that can tackle the barriers to engagement. Discussions focused on challenges facing an assessment, and then separately on defining a wish-list for an ideal assessment. However, the challenges identified ‘paired up’ with the wish-list ideas (i.e., one defined an issue, the other said that the ideal assessment would solve it). As such, the themes described (Table 5) were revealed from a combined analysis of both discussions. The themes group around categories of effectiveness, legitimacy, and practicality (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10: Themes (dark grey) and categories (light grey) highlighting the aspects important for a sustainability assessment — these were expressed by farm advisors as potential issues and in a wish-list for an ideal assessment to meet their needs when engaging with farmers on sustainability. Arrows indicate that each category of themes interacts with the others. Themes are described in Table 5.

TABLE 5: THEMES FROM FARM ADVISORS' DISCUSSIONS ON THE CHARACTERISTICS OF AN 'IDEAL' SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT TOOL.

Theme title (and category)	Theme description	Example comments
Clarity and relevance (Effective)	Having clear aims rather than trying to fit to what every different person wants is important. At the same time, those aims have to be relevant to farmers. The findings of the farm advisor survey illustrated that what is relevant to one farmer might not be to another, and that advisors themselves vary in terms of what they believe farmers will find most relevant. The look and feel of an assessment was deemed an important element in terms of getting farmers involved – design and language can help users feel comfortable and engaged, or if not done well, make them feel frustrated and/or alienated from the assessment's aims. Farmers may prefer visual approaches to communication, given the practical and spatial awareness skills their role requires and the interconnected and multi-faceted nature of sustainability.	<p>“What’s in it for them [farmers]?”</p> <p>“Yes, it’s just got to look good and be easy and quick to complete, and intuitive – there’s lots of programmes and you think ‘what do they mean by that?’”</p>
Pathways to change (Effective)	Outputs using benchmarking or levels to enable farmers to assess their performance, either versus a general standard or relative to other farms were important. These types of output can drive change and, in relation to this, participants highlighted the need to include suggestions for on-farm improvements alongside outputs – without this, farmers could be demotivated or feel helpless at seeing any relatively poor outcomes without ideas for achieving change.	<p>“Section specific themes whether you’re performing well, badly, or intermediate.”</p> <p>“Recommendations or at least a guide.”</p>

Theme title (and category)	Theme description	Example comments
Usability (Practical)	The efforts required of farmers to collect and collate the data required for the assessment, including the issue of getting farmers to undertake several tasks over time, which means that completing the assessment is not just a one-off effort on a ‘rainy afternoon’. How easy to use an assessment is, is fundamental to its success in driving change. Ease of data collection and input, verification to ensure inputs are valid, and a breakdown of the assessment into modules that could be undertaken bit by bit, were highlighted by participants as positive characteristics in this respect.	<p>“How many filing cabinets do you need to go through, piles of invoices?”</p> <p>“Depending on what the biodiversity assessment is then you need to do it about four times a year really.”</p>
Applicability and scope (Practical)	The boundaries of the systems covered by an assessment, and the types of system it is applicable to. Concern raised about exporting or importing sustainability problems (referred to as ‘burden shifting’ by Life Cycle Assessment practitioners). Flexibility to accommodate aspects of farming, such as the grazing of common land or sharing machinery between farms, was considered important to ensuring impacts are correctly identified and accounted for, avoiding burden shifting, and demonstrating the relevance of the assessment to their own system for farmers.	<p>“[not including off-farm grazing] could be very bad because then you’re importing or exporting your problems half the time because the animals will be moving between the two places.”</p>

Theme title (and category)	Theme description	Example comments
Feasibility (Practical)	Whether data are available to assess sustainability, discussing issues around the capacity for soil testing and the practicality of gathering data on shared resources such as common land — the issue of feasibility could also arise when data relating to outcomes are not available and modeling and other approaches are then required to estimate the relevant indicators. A related point was that farmers have to engage with multiple tools and assessments, involving costs in terms of money and time, confusion and a loss of interest — this makes additional assessments less feasible. A good assessment would draw on data already gathered and share data with other assessments and tools, becoming a one-stop-shop into which farmers can enter their data for their performance indicators once, and then not have to add anything more. Demonstrating links to current policy would add to the perceived relevance and usefulness of the assessment. The theme included the suggestion that not achieving this linkage could make a new assessment not only sub-optimal but actually negative, exacerbating existing barriers to engagement on sustainability.	<p>“If you were part of a big common like Black Mountains I don’t know where you’d stop and start with the biodiversity for instance”</p> <p>“One stop shop is probably — it could solve a lot of questions, a lot of challenges, but if it isn’t that it’s going to add to the confusion, add to the lack of data respect that we have and all the rest of it. It’s just going to exacerbate all of those barriers — it’s just going to make them worse.”</p>

Theme title (and category)	Theme description	Example comments
Transparency (Legitimate)	Potential concerns of farmers about how their data will be used and by whom, and beyond this whether they will trust the results that the tool provides — this is likely to be affected by the amount of data which have come from other sources, which might reduce a farmer’s confidence in the accuracy of the outcome. Participants also mentioned how poor results might lead to greater questioning. Questions asked specifically about the Global Farm Metric assessment demonstrated the importance of making methods fully visible to ensure legitimacy and avoid misunderstandings.	<p>“If data collection is automated and tells me as a farmer ‘you’re only 32%, we’re only going to give you peanuts’, I’d probably start getting a little bit feisty and start challenging the tool, because I haven’t put any data in to know where all this data’s come from — brilliant I never had to spend any time but — it’s usually the case isn’t it — if things are good and you’ve scored me well and you give me lots of money I wouldn’t question it. At least when people put the data in themselves, they have ownership.”</p> <p>“We probably all have farmers’ voices ringing in our ears saying, ‘Who has access to these data? Where do these data go? [others agreeing] How am I going to capture it? Why do you need to know about this? Do government get to see that?’ And no matter how many times you tell them it’s always ‘yeah, yeah, you would say that wouldn’t you?’ [sarcastically]”</p>
Robustness (Legitimate)	The quality of the assessment itself — the methods it applies and their basis and suitability — as well as to the issue of farmers entering incorrect or inaccurate data, through oversight, misunderstandings, or mistakes, or to avoid sharing negative information. Both the calculations made in any assessment tool and the quality of data put into them determine whether an assessment is robust.	<p>“A self-assessment model is fraught with danger for generating results which aren’t of much use to the individual business and are potentially hugely misleading at the industry level”</p> <p>“Sometimes it begs more questions than it answers — rubbish in, rubbish out. Who quality controls it and says ‘that can’t be right’”</p> <p>“Do you have different statistics for different types of farm for instance? So are hill farms and dairy and arable separated?”</p>

Theme title (and category)	Theme description	Example comments
Inclusivity	Sustainability is something that can be enabled through support and engagement beyond the farm — practically, in terms of drawing on the expertise of different groups and individuals to support data collection, and psychologically in terms of supporting the farmer as he or she tries to get a better overview of farm impacts and implement change. Drawing on the discussions of how sustainability assessments can affect challenges to engagement, benchmarking across farms can motivate group action to help those at the bottom. Inclusiveness can support tackling all challenges for assessment by bringing in wider expertise, knowledge, and resources. However, barriers to engagement such as farmer mindset, distrust and fear of external influence can be a bar to achieving inclusivity, making it challenging to achieve beyond the tried and tested approach of linking groups of farmers. Not having inclusivity may not worsen barriers to engagement but attempting inclusivity and failing may do.	<p>“So, for the sustainability stuff to work it needs input from more than one quarter, it needs you know, the school, the local vicar, whatever. And it works then. I think if only the farmer does it, I don’t think it works — people say ‘oh I don’t know what he’s doing’”</p> <p>“I suppose this is where you could — it’s what I like to try and do — is use other things — you could engage the local botany society and people like that who are quite happy to do bird counts — I mean, that’s what we do at home is that they do it for us, so I guess that’s a way of having better data as well. [response] You’ve got the National Parks as well, in that biodiversity part, there’s potential there.”</p> <p>“I had a good example of a dairy group in Herefordshire who were all benchmarking their businesses and the bottom one — they were sharing with each other and somebody came bottom — and the bottom one said ‘God, what do I do now?’ and the top two went and helped him. They actually helped him, they went to his farm, talked about the business — brilliant.”</p>

TABLE 6: CHARACTERISTICS OF A SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT HIGHLIGHTED BY FARM ADVISORS VERSUS CHARACTERISTICS USED TO EVALUATE CARBON FOOTPRINT TOOLS IN THE CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE WALES PROJECT (TAFT ET AL. 2018).

Characteristic highlighted by farm advisors	Aspects from previous Climate Smart Agriculture Wales study
Clarity and relevance	Intuitive, helpful, relevant, promoting of ongoing use
Pathways to change	NOT COVERED
Transparency	Transparent, accepted, secure
Robustness	Validated, current, sensitive, stable
Usability	Reliable, accessible, simple
Feasibility	NOT COVERED
Applicability and scope	Mainstream, comprehensive, adaptable
Inclusivity	NOT COVERED
NOT COVERED	Affordable

2.2.6.1. SYNTHESIS OF CRITERIA FOR EVALUATING SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENTS

Previous work evaluating agricultural carbon footprint calculators in Wales (Taft et al., 2018) considered characteristics of practicality (how affordable, scalable, accessible, stable, adaptable and reliable the tool is); usability, and ability to enable use (how intuitive, helpful, accepted, relevant, sensitive, simple, and promoting of ongoing use the tool is); rigour and completeness (how secure, current, validated, transparent, mainstream, and comprehensive the tool is). These criteria were taken from evaluation frameworks used by Hall et al. (2010) and Whittaker et al. (2013). They can be mapped to the aspects of assessments highlighted as important by farm advisors (Table 6).

Overall, criteria for a sustainability assessment identified by advisors matched closely the criteria previously used to assess carbon footprint calculation tools. However, three aspects of sustainability assessment highlighted by farm advisors — inclusivity, pathways to change, and feasibility — were not considered in the CSA Wales criteria. The absence of the first two aspects is likely to reflect the specific farm advisor perspective (versus that of researchers looking at tool capabilities) in which an assessment is part of a process of change undertaken in the context of other stakeholders who could provide supporting resources (or be the source of problems).

In the workshop, discussions on feasibility considered a wide range of issues, relating to the availability and process of data collection and the pressures on farmers to engage with multiple tools and assessments. This aspect of context was beyond the scope of the CSA evaluation which focused on the carbon footprinting tools themselves, rather than the data they required or their use alongside other requirements being made of farmers.

One area was covered in CSA Wales but not in the workshop discussions, which was the issue of the affordability of a tool — this aspect was outside the scope of the current workshop discussions, which focused on what an assessment should and shouldn’t do, rather than on its cost. However, financial pressures and costs of change were highlighted as barriers to engagement on sustainability and so an assessment which is expensive is likely to face problems attracting users, unless funds are available to cover these costs for farmers.

The views of farm advisors analysed here have highlighted the importance when evaluating assessments and tools of considering several aspects of the context in which assessments are used (the concurrent use of other tools and assessments by farmers and the burden of this, the availability of required data, a knowledge exchange process with change as a goal, and a rural community — including other farmers — able to support assessments practically, socially and with expertise). The inclusion of these elements in future evaluations of on-farm decision support tools would be valuable in driving improvements in usage and in outcomes.

The findings relating to the characteristics required of sustainability assessments can be compared with the solutions put forward to the three challenges to engagement most likely to be addressed by a sustainability assessment: complexity of sustainability, advisor knowledge, experience and perspective, and farmer knowledge and understanding (Fig. 8). Leaving aside solutions relating to the context of engagement, the themes ‘clarify the issue’ and ‘highlight the value of actions’ were key knowledge exchange approaches, backed up by ‘learning from others’ and providing ‘relevant and actionable information’.

The solutions to barriers to engagement are most closely relevant to the ‘effective’ category of required assessment characteristics (clarify the issue; highlight value of action; relevant and actionable information) although the last especially also requires the assessment to be practical and legitimate. Learning from others as an approach links to the theme of inclusivity (Fig. 11).

FIG. 11: HOW THEMES (DARK GREY) AND CATEGORIES (LIGHT GREY) RELATING TO THE REQUIRED CHARACTERISTICS OF A SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT FIT WITH SOLUTIONS PUT FORWARD BY FARM ADVISORS TO TACKLE KNOWLEDGE AND COGNITIVE BARRIERS TO ENGAGING WITH FARMERS ON SUSTAINABILITY (WHITE RECTANGLES).

This comparison indicates that the solutions representing approaches to engagement (clarify the issue and highlight value of action) can be achieved through providing a strong concept of sustainability and its value, and by providing information (and support) for concrete change; in effect by sharing a conceptual framework of sustainability with farmers.

This clarity and link to practice is necessary for a formal assessment but achieving it does not require such an assessment. Relevant and actionable information can also be linked to such a framework, which can be used in inclusive processes of engagement.

An effective, practical, and legitimate sustainability assessment can boost engagement by enabling benchmarking (learning from others) and quantifying issues and the impacts of change (highlight value of action, relevant and actionable information, clarify the issue). On the other hand, a sub-optimal or poorly executed sustainability assessment might, according to advisors, have negative impacts on the barriers to engagement and to change. Given that barriers to engagement are likely to be larger for farmers on smaller farms, those who are older, and those with disabilities (Hurley et al., 2022), they are most likely to be negatively affected by the experience of a difficult assessment.

As such, it may be best to ensure clarity around the concept of sustainability and to highlight the value of actions to improve it before asking farmers to undertake a formal assessment (Fig. 12). Whichever methods are subsequently used with farmers to drive change, farmers will already know what sustainability is and why they need to pursue it. This de-couples engagement on sustainability from the characteristics of a given assessment. Even if weaknesses in an assessment do cause problems, this would be less likely to create damaging impacts for sustainability engagement or change more generally. Indeed, the positive effects on barriers to engagement of a clear vision / understanding of the value of sustainability, can instead drive willingness to engage and change even before further interventions are attempted. In this way, the positivity generated by engagement with a clear, holistic conceptual framework can make any further methods applied (such as sustainability assessment, group advice, or information sharing through demonstration farms) more likely to succeed and contribute to driving change.

FIG. 12: BARRIERS TO ENGAGEMENT AND HOW THEY INTERACT WITH THE TWO DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF A SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT I) THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK UNDERLYING THE ASSESSMENT AND ACTIONS BASED ON UNDERSTANDING IT (BLUE SHADES) II) THE DEVELOPMENT AND USE OF AN ASSESSMENT TOOL BASED ON THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK, THE CHALLENGES TO ACHIEVING THIS, AND THE ACTIONS BASED ON IT (ORANGE SHADES).

In summary, introducing a clear conceptual framework that highlights the value of sustainability can act to reduce barriers to engagement and change. Attempting to deliver a sustainability assessment at the same time as introducing the concept of sustainability faces barriers and can create feedbacks of negativity that may increase those barriers. This could affect both the willingness of farmers to engage as well as the process of assessment and the chances of it leading to change (Fig. 12). Introducing a sustainability framework and giving it time to create positive feedbacks which reduce barriers to engagement can solidify support for sustainability — this support is then less likely to be harmed by later experience with an imperfect sustainability tool or assessment.

The development and use of a sustainability framework by farm advisors can be visualised as the initial step in driving change (Fig. 13). This initial step is often overlooked in attempts to change farming practices and outcomes, but the evidence gathered from farm advisors indicate its key role in reducing barriers to engagement, in the success of sustainability assessments, and ultimately in the transformation towards sustainable farming.

FIG. 13: APPLYING LEARNINGS FROM WORK WITH FARM ADVISORS TO HIGHLIGHT THE CORE ROLE OF A SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK AS THE INITIAL STEP IN DRIVING CHANGE IN FARMING.

2.3. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The Global Farm Metric framework has been developed with farmers to define sustainability holistically while breaking down the concept into parts which can be related to the practical reality of a farm. These characteristics align with farm advisors' emphasis on the need for clarity to address the complexity of sustainability as an issue, and the need to enable farmers to understand the value of moving towards more sustainable farming. However, before the current project began, the framework was often seen as synonymous with the GFM research tool, which provides an overview of the sustainability performance of farms as a proof of concept of how holistic monitoring of farm sustainability can inform and drive change.

The work carried out with farm advisors in Wales reported here, has revealed that the GFM framework alone could have a key role in driving change, while sustainability assessments (whichever tools are used) must meet a number of requirements in order for their positive impacts to outweigh the risks associated with their use. Engaging farmers using a conceptual framework for understanding sustainability and starting to use it to frame on-farm knowledge exchange, can drive change itself. In addition, it can reduce barriers to engagement with farmers which might otherwise hamper the effective

use of formal assessments.

Beyond the current project, the GFM framework will be revised with this independent role in mind, to maximise its potential as a knowledge exchange method for sustainability. Future development with farm advisors will be undertaken to hone the framework and to understand how it can most effectively be used in ordinary consultations with farmers. As a first step in this process, within this project, the GFM wheel – a visual interpretation of the GFM framework – will be used in reports produced for farmers by the Wye and Usk Foundation, to provide them with a conceptual overview of what sustainability is and what it involves. Revisions to the framework will draw on the views of advisors discussed above and on farmer and advisor feedback from this trial (see following sections) and wider trials of the GFM assessment as a whole. Finally, the required characteristics of a sustainability assessment defined by farm advisors will be used to frame the feedback from farmers relating to their experience of using the GFM tool, to evaluate its strengths and weaknesses.

3. On-farm trial

This section covers the following activities (Table 1): Trial the Global Farm Metric framework and assessment tool with 10–20 farmers in the Monmouthshire area to gain an overview of their current sustainability performance across economic, social, and environmental categories

The on-farm trial used the GFM framework and associated GFM research tool to assess whole-farm sustainability on eleven farms in Monmouthshire, representing a range of farming systems.

The GFM framework is intended to provide a common language for farmers, supply chain actors, policymakers, and the public to understand sustainability — it represents a holistic view of sustainability, considering environmental, economic, and social aspects. Its aims and a strategic overview can be found here: <https://www.globalfarmmetric.org/reports/2022-brochure/>.

Based on the GFM framework, the GFM research tool was developed to demonstrate and explore how sustainability could best be assessed on-farm across all categories of the framework. It is this tool which was applied on the Monmouthshire farms.

This section describes the trial process and details the aims, approach, and nature of the GFM research tool (including its limitations) before providing a whole trial summary of assessment results. Section 4 of the report subsequently focuses on trial feedback methods and results and discusses the views shared by farmers and farm advisors, their implications and resulting next steps.

3.1. APPROACH

3.1.2. THE ASSESSMENT PROCESS

Farmers were signed up to the trial as volunteers via a webinar introducing the project aims and approach and the GFM framework and tool. Others were identified via the networks of the Wye and Usk Foundation (WUF), Farming Connect (FC) and NRW. Although farmers were not paid or otherwise rewarded for their involvement at the start of the trial, those taking part received free soil testing, and in addition to the GFM assessment, trial farms had the opportunity to receive a free carbon footprint assessment using the AgreCalc carbon footprinting tool.

Farmers who agreed to participate in the trial were asked to register to gain access to the online tool. The GFM research tool was designed as a self-assessment tool, however, in this trial further support was provided in order to show (versus other trials without such support):

1. The extent to which data completeness and quality, time involved, and problems experienced could be reduced by the provision of support from a farm advisor
2. Based on i) to identify the areas of the assessment which farmers struggled with most and to get a first-hand account from the advisor about those challenges and (from their experience) how they felt other farmers would cope with the assessment, if tackling it alone.

A WUF farm advisor supported farmers through the assessment process. This support varied from farm to farm but included:

- Data collection including undertaking soil data (infiltration tests, earth worms counts etc.)
- Going through the assessment itself with the farmer on-farm, and/or troubleshooting aspects of the online assessment which the farmer struggled to complete alone.

The Global Farm Metric trials team was also available on the phone and by email to provide advice and support to the farmers and to the farm advisor. Online, tailored training on the GFM research tool was given to the farm advisor and other partners involved at the start of the trial.

On completing the assessment, farmers are provided with:

- Their automatically generated individual assessment results
- The group summary report, highlighting key results across the farms in the trial (anonymised)
- A report from the Wye and Usk Foundation farm advisor highlighting opportunities for change and improvement based on each farm's performance
- An invitation to a presentation and discussion of the trial at the 3 Salmons Hotel, Usk, with WUF and FC farm advisors, a specialist carbon footprinting advisor, and the GFM trials team. This event (13th September 2022) provided an informal opportunity to receive advice and provide feedback, and for the team to thank the farmers for their participation.

3.1.3. THE GLOBAL FARM METRIC RESEARCH TOOL

The research tool is a development of the ELM Sustainability Assessment (ELSA) tool, with an online interface for farmers to input data and receive results. The information on the tool presented here is drawn from the 2021 report 'Constructing the ELM Sustainability Assessment (ELSA) tool' (Smith and Smith, 2021) and more details of the tool can be found in that report. The GFM research tool was developed with some key aims in mind:

- To provide a holistic assessment of on-farm sustainability across the GFM framework categories of environmental, social, and economic sustainability (Table 7)
- To move towards a farmer-led approach (self-assessment)
- To focus on outcomes-based metrics where possible
- To balance data needs with farmer workload (simplicity)
- To use existing protocols and schemes to provide methods where relevant and useful (not re-inventing the wheel)

As indicated in Table 7 and described below, to date the tool still relies on a number of practice-based questions. For GHG emissions and nutrient flows this is unavoidable as emissions/nutrient loss cannot practically be measured directly on each farm and must be modelled based on detailed information about the farm system and its management.

Data are entered into the tool online by the farmer (a data requirement sheet is provided so that farmers can see what data they need before they log in to complete the assessment — they can then gather the required information in advance). The tool generates an immediate set of results. Their data and these results are not stored — the farmer must download a csv file which contains all the data she/he has inputted. This can be uploaded again online if the farmer wishes to view the findings again. This means that farmers retain ownership and control of their data.

In the current GFM research tool trials, farmers send their complete data files into the trials team, who produce the averaged 'group summary' findings described in this report for the eleven Monmouthshire farms in the trial.

Sustainability Category	Tool Indicator
Productivity	Physical outputs, financial outputs (S); Gross and net margins
Soil	Soil organic matter (S); Soil structure and infiltration (S); Soil biodiversity (S); Soil erosion (S)
Water	Sources of water used (S); Irrigation methods (S); Practices to reduce pollution and flooding (S); Water quality (S)
Air and climate	GHG emissions by source
Energy and resource use efficiency	Fossil fuel use by enterprise (S); Renewable energy use (S); 'Human edible' energy efficiency; Waste and recycling (S)
Nutrient management	Farm gate NPK balance - input/output ratio for nutrient management efficiency (S)
Livestock management	Feed conversion ratios for livestock types (S); Vet and med expenditures; Natural behaviour (S); Housing conditions (S); Feeding practices (S); Staff resources (S); Animal health (S)
Plant and crop health	Diversity in crop rotation and grassland (S); Pesticide usage (S)
Biodiversity	Planned biodiversity (S); Farm habitats (S); Wild biodiversity (S)
Social	Education provision (S); Level of community engagement (S); Level of public access (S)
Human	Levels of employment and working hours (S) Workforce skills and training (S) Workforce health and wellbeing (S)

TABLE 7: CATEGORIES OF SUSTAINABILITY AND THEIR INDICATORS IN THE GFM RESEARCH TOOL (TAKEN FROM SMITH AND SMITH (2021) WITH PERMISSION OF THE AUTHORS). S = INDICATORS INCLUDED IN-TOOL SCORING — OTHER INDICATORS ARE PROVIDED TO THE USER BUT NOT SCORED AT PRESENT.

3.1.4. SCORING

For the GFM framework marked with an 'S' in Table 7 above, the GFM research tool provides scores based either on national benchmarks or on expert opinion. Scores of 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100% are given for each question / dataset that contributes to the overall category score. These individual scores are added up and divided by their total number — for example, if there are two individual scores these are added and divided by two.

In some systems/contexts, specific questions contributing to a category score will not be relevant, and in this case the tool does not include the individual score — this avoids biasing the outcome with 'zero' scores that in fact represent non-relevant aspects.

Question and category scores are nominally evenly weighted, however, as some category scores average more individual scores than others (include results from more questions), in effect where this is the case the response to an individual question will have a smaller impact on the total than when fewer individual scores contribute. Responses are scored with the aim that a score of 50% represents an average outcome. For each set of results in Section 4.3, the relevant part of the scoring table (Table 8) is presented to show clearly the basis for the scores returned in that category.

TABLE 8: DETAILS OF THE QUESTIONS/DATA THAT CONTRIBUTE TO CATEGORY SCORES, AND THE BASIS FOR THE CONVERSION OF ANSWERS INTO SCORES. NB AS NOTED IN MAIN TEXT, IF A QUESTION IS NOT ANSWERED, THE SCORE IS CALCULATED NOT TAKING THAT ANSWER INTO ACCOUNT (E.G., A NON-ANSWER WILL NOT BE RECORDED AS ZERO). DATA COLLECTED AND DISPLAYED BUT NOT SCORED ARE NOT INCLUDED IN THE TABLE BELOW, EXCEPT TO HIGHLIGHT THAT AIR AND CLIMATE IS INCLUDED IN THE TOOL BUT NOT SCORED. REFER TO THE ORIGINAL REPORT (SMITH AND SMITH 2021) FOR FULL REFERENCES RELATING TO CITATIONS IN THE TABLE.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Productivity	Financial Output	Two questions i) What is the ratio of the price obtained to the standard price (for all farm produce) ii) How have net assets (total assets <u>less</u> total liabilities) changed in the last year?	Benchmarking using Nix Farm Management Handbook plus some prices from Organic Farm Management Handbook
Productivity	Farm resilience	Ten questions on investment, variations in profit margins, sources of farm income, on-farm data collection and use, farm performance and long-term survival	Expert opinion
Soil	Soil analysis	Two questions: i) how often <u>do you undertake</u> soil analysis and ii) results of Soil Organic Matter (SOM) analysis	Scores based on expert opinion (i) and standard guidance for interpreting SOM levels in the UK (ii)
Soil	Soil structure / infiltration	VESS soil test plus rate of drainage of water through soil (infiltration) test	Scores based on standard guidance on interpreting these tests
Soil	Soil biodiversity	Based on three earthworm sampling questions: i) Large vertical burrows or middens present? ii) no. of adults and juveniles present in sample, iii) no. of ecotypes present	Expert opinion
Soil	Soil erosion	Seven questions which look at the production of a soil erosion risk map, the % of land affected by soil erosion, and management factors affecting erosion, such as % bare land, timing of harvesting, cultivation methods and use of buffer strips.	Expert opinion
Water	Water sources	Sources of water used on farms and the proportion used from each of these sources	Based on data for average UK farm mains / abstracted water %
Water	Water quality	Irrigation questions (type, area on which applied, water quality checks, source of water), percent of yes vs no answers to	List of options from Newell Price et al (2011) — DEFRA project on inventory of

		whether the farm uses a list of potential practices for reducing water pollution (N/A options not included)	methods to reduce diffuse water pollution, GHG emissions and ammonia
Water	Water biota	Questions on aquatic life for each water body type on farm	Expert opinion based on test results, including based on guidelines from FreshWater Watch
Energy and Resource Use	Energy sources and use	Total energy use per enterprise converted to Mega Joules and the sources of energy (proportion renewable)	Benchmarked from study of energy use of 950 farms (Williams et al 2006)
Energy and Resource Use	Renewable energy production	Percentage of on-farm energy use from renewables produced on farm	Expert opinion
Energy and Resource Use	Waste management †	Three questions on i) % of non-organic farm wastes recycled, ii) disposal of unwanted medicines, iii) the existence of a written waste strategy	Expert opinion
Nutrient Management †		Automatically calculates farm-gate NPK ratios based on Initial data collection sheet information on imports and exports of crops, livestock, and livestock products, and their associated (generic average) NPK contents. Inputs of N (from generic average data) include N fixation, atmospheric inputs and purchased nutrients. Score based on NPK surpluses or deficits	The score is based on Guide to Nutrient Budgeting (IOTA 2015)
Animal Husbandry	Feed conversion ratios	The energy value (MJ) of livestock exported for human consumption is calculated from Initial Data collection sheet, as is the energy value (MJ) of feed imported. This is calculated as the edible energy (MJ) fed per unit of human-edible animal product produced (MJ) using data from Wilkinson (2011)	Expert opinion
Animal Husbandry	Natural Behaviour	Information on access to pasture/range for different species. Questions: i) months of access, ii) hours grazing per day in a season, iii) access to outdoor run if not at pasture, then questions on the ability of the animals to perform natural behaviour when feeding, resting and social/comfort, and a question on abnormal behaviour	Expert opinions
Animal Husbandry	Housing	Eight questions on housing stocking densities, condition of bedding material, design of milking parlours (for dairy only), animal handling facilities,	Expert opinions
Animal Husbandry	Feeding practices	Five questions, on available space for feeding, feeding according to physiological needs, the proportion of roughage and availability of water.	Expert opinions
Animal Husbandry	Staff resources	Three questions on staff resources for the livestock enterprise: i) frequency of checking livestock for signs of illness and injury, ii) level of training of Stockpeople , iii) no. full-time equivalents looking after livestock – using standard man	Expert <u>opinion</u> : John Nix Farm Management Handbook (2010) data used to compare staff time per livestock type to the standard.

		hours per types of livestock a calc is made of how many FTEs handling livestock might be expected for farm and compared to actual	
Animal Husbandry	Health and welfare	Twenty questions on approaches to vaccination, antibiotic use, anti-parasite treatments and management, mortality and culling rates; longevity of breeding animals, lameness incidence, hair/fleece problems, mastitis incidence (in dairy animals), feed related disorders, conception rates, sanitary status; somatic cell counts (for dairy systems) and performance at the abattoir	
Plant and Crop Health	Diversity in crop rotation and grassland	Two questions on diversity in the crop rotation and diversity in grassland	Expert opinion
Plant and Crop Health	Pesticide use	Average number of spray rounds per crop type	Compared to national figures from DEFRA Pesticide Usage Surveys
Biodiversity	Planned biodiversity	Score based on average of the number of crop species/varieties present and the number of livestock species/breeds present (an additional variety/breed counted as plus one, and same for an additional species — so not differentiated)	Expert opinion
Biodiversity	Farm habitats and management	Two questions i) which of a list of practices for biodiversity (drawn from Cool Farm Tool list) are carried out, ii) No. of habitats present (habitats from 'UK Hab' habitat classification system plus (for arable land) Level 5 habitat classifications including types of <u>margin</u> , iii) % non-productive land	Expert opinion
Biodiversity	Wild biodiversity	Scored based on outcomes (no. of species) of a bird (Big Farmland Bird Count method but only using presence/absence, not highest no. seen) and a butterfly survey (UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme method, through summer)	Expert opinion
Social	Education provision	Two questions: i) hosting educational activities, e.g., farm walks, educational workshops, visits from local schools, Forest schools or Care farming, ii) apprenticeships and work placements	Expert opinion
Social	Level of community engagement	No. of community events hosted or contributed to, such as Open Farm Sunday, farm walks, local craft fairs, fetes, festivals, barn-dances, barbecues, debates and discussions, means of communication used to connect with the community, such as information boards, website, social media, farm shop, bed and breakfast, whether farm sells produce direct to customers on-farm, number of visitors to farm per year	Expert opinion
Social	Level of public access	Single question on level of access, ranging from none to open access	Expert opinion

Human	Employment and working hours	No. FT and PT staff (including family members and volunteers) and total number of hours worked in the 12-month period, converted to Full Time Equivalents (240 days/year or 1872 hours) per 100ha	Compared to regional average from Morison et al (2005)
Human	Workforce skills and training	Number of training days all staff have had over <u>12 month</u> period	Training days compared to average training days from Statista.com (2017)
Human	Workforce health and well-being	Eight questions: social activities that involve the staff, such as shared meals, coffee breaks, social media groups, social events, daily/weekly meetings, team-building days etc., the total no. sick days recorded in the 12-month period (converted to % of FTE), remaining questions on working conditions, covering risk assessments, exposure to hazardous chemicals, workload, sharing workload with neighbouring farmers and amount of holiday. Plus, calc of average no. of hours worked per FTE versus the working time directive	Sick days benchmarked versus national average for agric. forestry, and fishing sector for 2017, hours worked compared with Working Time Directive
Air quality and climate	GHG emissions	Not scored – calculates GHG footprint of products (crops, livestock and livestock products) using standard data for production of agricultural commodities in the UK and based on the number of livestock or tonnes of crops exported from the farm	Data presented in bar charts as kgCO ₂ e for each livestock / crop type

3.1.5. TOOL LIMITATIONS

For all modelling and assessment processes, it is good practice to highlight the limitations of the methods used. There is a famous phrase which says that ‘all models are wrong’: models and assessments are always simplifications of reality, and their outcomes should be the starting point for improvement, decision-making, and evaluation, to be treated critically as part of a human process of change.

Models and assessments cannot and should not be used as a substitute for human responsibility in decision-making, but rather provide valuable information and insight to support such choices. Using any assessment without proper understanding of context or limits is highly risky — this is why change in any sector requires the actors involved to be committed, well-resourced, and collaborative in moving towards shared goals. In this circumstance, assessments and models can guide change and highlight issues, rather than being applied without critical interpretation or human processes of engagement.

Beyond this general caveat associated with the use of all models and assessments, this section provides an overview of some limitations of the GFM research tool (many of which are also limitations of other existing assessments and models):

- As described above, a key issue for the GFM research tool has been the trade-off between accuracy and scope inherent in providing a holistic assessment of all sustainability categories. In particular, this means that the greenhouse gas emissions and nutrient management scores are based on relatively simple modelling from generic data, rather than detailed mechanistic modelling of the range of farm practices that can affect emissions and nutrient losses. In this trial, farmers were offered the chance to provide data for a free AgreCalc carbon footprint to give them emissions results which take into account their practices (and would adjust with changes in those practices). Including AgreCalc carbon footprinting in the trial, enabled us to evaluate the extent to which data already collected for the GFM research tool assessment could provide farmers with a ‘head start’ in completing AgreCalc, and the extent to which collecting data for both assessments at once would be practical. This approach reflects ongoing work by the GFM

research team to align GFM research tool data collection requirements to the needs of key pre-existing carbon-footprinting and farm management decision support systems and models. The aim is that data collected for GFM could then be used by farmers in these other contexts, reducing duplication of effort for them (the outcomes of this work were not part of this trial).

- The second challenge for the research tool is the current reliance on practice-based questions for the assessment of some categories beyond Air and climate and Nutrient management — the revision of indicators underway at present will seek to move further towards the goal of outcome-based indicators, which reduces the need for interpretive scoring of practices and for the collection of detailed farm management data.
- The choice of scoring granularity (0, 25, 50, 75, 100%) and the fitting of scores to question responses and data is often based on expert opinion. The broad scoring bands reflect a cautious approach to evaluating data and, where possible, benchmarking to available data underpins scoring judgements (see Table 8). However, different experts could give different opinions on the fitting of scores to the data and on the weight given to each individual question score, and this must be taken into account when considering the results. Again, an important outcome of the current trials and GFM revision will be to focus more on outcome-based indicator values reported directly and to reduce the use of scores. Where scoring is applied, the aim is to maximise clarity by reporting its basis alongside results (as here) as well as working to revise its evidential basis as required.
- The assessment boundaries are farm gate to farm gate, which creates some restrictions — in particular, land rented out is not evaluated except as an income source, as impacts associated with it would be allocated to the tenant — this is not an issue if the tenant also completes the assessment but may lead to an underestimate of impacts from a given area if this was not the case. Additionally, common land is not currently included in assessments, and this aspect of the tool is under review.
- Benchmarking between farms is possible as the GFM involves the collection of common data for every farm. However (and this challenge applies to all benchmarking of farm performance), farms vary in so many respects that it is

arguable whether variations in performance reflect differences in the choice/implementation of systems/practices or just differences in farm characteristics and context. One issue well known to the Life Cycle Assessment community is that, if off-farm impacts are not fully and accurately taken into account, more extensive, low input production systems may appear less sustainable than high input systems, as the impacts of the majority of their activities will arise on-farm. In contrast, many impacts of an intensive high input system (for example, a system which imports all its feed) will occur off farm and not within the farm gate. As a result, intensive, high input systems may appear more sustainable just because their impacts are pushed upstream of the farm. This is just one example of how benchmarking across varying farms can create misleading comparisons and potential unintended consequences if action is then taken on this basis.

- In common with all assessments, and especially as a self-assessment, the GFM research tool findings can only be as good as the data entered. Given the amount of data required, data input mistakes and omissions are always possible and, if they do not present as extreme values for a given datapoint or create unusual results, may be overlooked despite checks. This must be borne in mind when reviewing the results of any modelling or assessment.
- As described above, in the GFM research tool ‘non-answers’ (questions not relevant to a given farm) do not have a negative impact on category scores as, where this is the case, the whole question is skipped in the scoring process. However, if many questions are unanswered, scores will be based on fewer data points and, therefore, become more vulnerable to error and less well-founded in terms of the evidence underlying them. Again, this is

important to remember, especially when reviewing data at a group summary level, as here.

3.2. FINDINGS

This section provides a whole-trial level summary of assessment results. These findings should be considered in the context of the previous sections on the role and limits of the GFM research tool and of sustainability assessments in general.

Average scores from across the eleven farms (Fig. 14) engaged in the trial showed highest levels of performance in animal husbandry, plant and crop health, productivity, and soil. Performance in social, water, energy and resource use, and nutrient management categories was lower. However, for individual categories there was often a wide range of scoring (e.g., for nutrient management in particular). This is likely to reflect the diversity of farming systems included in the trial but the high scores of some farms suggest potential for improvement by those with lower scores. Given climate change predictions for more frequent and more severe extreme weather events, and the recent focus on the pollution of Welsh rivers, the categories of water and nutrient management stand out as important areas for improvement from these broad overview results.

In the following sections, average results across trial farms are looked at category by category. Note that no score is given for the air and climate category, as the simple modelling of greenhouse gas emissions within the tool is based only on the number of livestock and inputs to the system. As such, it would be misleading in terms of actual emissions and the options for change which could alter the results. Six farmers in this trial were supported to receive AgreCalc emissions estimates for their farms as part of the trial, but these results are beyond the scope of this report.

3.2.1. PRODUCTIVITY

Looking at the two scores which are combined to give the overall score for productivity (financial outputs and resilience) (Fig. 15a) indicates an overall relatively positive position for the farms involved in the trial. Of course, this snapshot does not capture all aspects of financial performance (Fig 15b highlights what the scores include) but provides some indication of farm resilience.

Farms had between two to four income sources. If inputs were to become unavailable, 70% of farmers felt that their farms would continue to function at a reduced scale, with 30% not affected. Of more concern is that 70% of farmers reported that they do not have a business plan and 80% that they do not have a succession plan (20% are yet to agree one). With an ageing farming population in Wales, the lack of succession plans highlights the need to attract and train the next generation of farmers — including providing them with realistic routes to access the land they need to ensure food security in Wales for the future.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Productivity	Financial Output	Two questions i) What is the ratio of the price obtained to the standard price (for all farm produce) ii) How have net assets (total assets <u>less</u> total liabilities) changed in the last year?	Benchmarking using data from Nix Farm Management Handbook plus some prices from Organic Farm Management Handbook
Productivity	Farm resilience	Ten questions on investment, variations in profit margins, sources of farm income, on-farm data collection and use, farm performance and long-term survival	Expert opinion

FIG 15: AVERAGE SCORES FOR PRODUCTIVITY INDICATORS (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR.

3.2.2. SOIL

The indicator scores within the soil category (Fig. 16) suggest relatively good performance, but with a wide range of scores in relation to soil organic matter (SOM). Given this range, increasing SOM may be a promising area for improvement for lower scoring farms, given the potential shown by the group for high scores. However, again it must be borne in mind that these data include a range of farm systems, which accounts for some of the variation shown.

Within the soil structure indicator, average infiltration rate was 2.67 mins (min: 1 minute, max: 6.4 minutes) versus guidance suggesting that for soils in good health water should drain away within 2–5 minutes for light or medium soils, whereas for a heavy clay soil with poor structure it could take 20 minutes or longer. SOM testing found an average of 2.25% (min: 1.16 max: 3.71) across trial farms, which is in line with a UK average of between 1 and 7% according to the Farm Carbon Toolkit.

FIG 16: AVERAGE SCORES FOR SOIL INDICATORS (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR. SOM = SOIL ORGANIC MATTER

In relation to soil biodiversity, the average number of earthworm burrows per sample was one, with an average of five worms per sample versus a UK national average of 9. Forty two percent of farms have all three earthworm ecotypes in their samples, 33% have two and 25% have one. To provide some context for the low observed earthworm abundance, research published this year suggests that earthworm abundance in UK fields may be extremely patchy and often driven by factors other than soil quality (Hodson et al., 2021). In the light of this study and as part of a constant updating of the GFM tool, the use of earthworm abundance as a soil health indicator is under review.

Responses on soil erosion indicated that 60% of trial farms have assessed that there is an erosion risk and are acting on it, while 40% have not assessed erosion. Of the 60% who have assessed that they face erosion risk, between 1–10% of their land was estimated to be affected. In relation to this, it is positive that 83% of trial farmers are using reduced cultivation methods, while only a small proportion of land is affected. However, for those farmers who have not done so already, assessing erosion should be a priority on land where there is a high risk of soil loss.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Soil	Soil organic matter	Two questions: i) how often <u>do you undertake</u> soil analysis and ii) results of Soil Organic Matter (SOM) analysis	Scores based on expert opinion (i) and standard guidance for interpreting SOM levels in the UK (ii)
Soil	Soil structure	VESS soil test plus rate of drainage of water through soil (infiltration) test, plus answers to questions on soil erosion: production of a soil erosion risk map, the % of land affected by soil erosion, and management factors affecting erosion, such as % bare land, timing of harvesting, cultivation methods and use of buffer strips.	Scores based on standard guidance on interpreting these tests
Soil	Soil biodiversity	Based on three earthworm sampling questions: i) Large vertical burrows or middens present? ii) no. of adults and juveniles present in sample, iii) no. of ecotypes present	Expert opinion

3.2.3. WATER

Overall, the group received an average score for the water category (Fig. 17a). The indicators contributing to the overall water category average varied considerably: ‘sources’ — scored based on the proportion of mains and extracted water used as a negative impact — scored quite poorly, with the group on average using 65% abstracted water and 35% from the mains. Only 0.7% of the water used by the group was sourced from rainwater (0.5%) or recycled grey water (0.2%). The ‘quality’ indicator carried a medium score, and ‘biota’ received the highest score. There was a wide range within the scores for all indicators, again highlighting the importance of looking at individual question responses making up each score (Fig. 17b), and of exploring results at farm-level to drive change.

Findings suggest that areas farmers could improve include finding more sustainable sources of water and taking action that would help increase water quality. As climate change brings increased risk of water shortages and flooding, it will be ever-more important to reduce water use, especially from extraction and the mains.

Water management practices, which are used as a proxy for water quality, are also a point for improvement. Approximately half of the group manage their water using practices associated with positive water quality. For example, 50% monitor their pH frequently, 55% use clover and buffer strips (both in-field and riparian) and 40% have established new hedges. Uptake of more permanent and resource intensive practices were lower: 30% of the group have converted arable land to woodland and un-grazed grass, while only 15% use woody dams and floodwater storage. Soil management for reduced water pollution tells a similar story: 60% of the group have assessed erosion risk and are acting on this knowledge to reduce soil loss and water pollution.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Water	Water sources	Sources of water used on farms and the proportion used from each of these sources	Based on data for average UK farm mains / abstracted water %
Water	Water quality	Irrigation questions (type, area on which applied, water quality checks, source of water), percent of yes vs no answers to whether the farm uses a list of potential practices for reducing water pollution (N/A options not included)	List of options from Newell Price et al (2011) – DEFRA project on inventory of methods to reduce diffuse water pollution, GHG emissions and ammonia
Water	Water biota	Questions on aquatic life for each water body type on farm	Expert opinion based on test results, including based on guidelines from FreshWater.Watch

FIG 17: AVERAGE SCORES FOR WATER INDICATORS (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR.

3.2.4. ENERGY AND RESOURCE USE

Overall, the group gained an average score for the energy and resource use category (Fig. 18), with quite a high range of category scores. This variation was similarly reflected in the energy production and waste management indicators. However, the group’s score was just below average for performance in the energy source and use indicator, with relatively little variation. The waste management indicator told a more positive story, with 70% of the group reporting recycling over 80% of their non-organic waste.

With the cost of diesel rising as a result of current supply issues, switching to more sustainable and renewable energy sources can not only help reduce emissions, but also have positive economic outcomes. However, it is important to take into account the quantity and efficiency of fuel use, as high levels of external inputs can indicate the vulnerability of the system to changes in conditions outside the farm.

Results suggest that improvements could be made in energy production, source, and usage. The group’s main source of energy was red diesel, accounting for approximately 80% of total MJ used. Following this was non-renewable electricity (8%), heating oil (4%) and wood fuel (3%), with DERV diesel, petrol, and renewable sources supplying 2% of total energy used.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Energy and Resource Use	Energy sources and use	Total energy use per enterprise converted to Mega Joules and the sources of energy (proportion renewable)	Benchmarked from study of energy use of 950 farms (Williams et al 2006)
Energy and Resource Use	Renewable energy production	Percentage of on-farm energy use from renewables produced on farm	Expert opinion
Energy and Resource Use	Waste management	Three questions on i) % of non-organic farm wastes recycled, ii) disposal of unwanted medicines, iii) the existence of a written waste strategy	Expert opinion

FIG 18: AVERAGE SCORES FOR ENERGY AND RESOURCE USE INDICATORS (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR.

3.2.5. NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT

Nutrient balance is the single indicator of the nutrient management category (Fig 19). Overall, the group had a wide range of scores for nutrient balance, averaging mid-range performance. However, the majority of the group (approximately 65%) scored poorly for nutrient usage, with an overall surplus of NPK calculated when assessing whole farm balances.

However, a range of results is reflected in the individual nutrient usage rating (see Fig 19b for details). For Phosphorus (P) and Potassium (K), 60% of the group scored ‘poor-very poor’. However, the remaining 40% for P and 30% for K scored ‘very good-excellent’, with 10% of the group scoring ‘good-average’ for K. Nitrogen (N) use similarly shows clustering at the extreme ends of the spectrum, with 70% scoring ‘poor-very poor’, 20%

‘average-poor’ and 10% ‘very good-excellent’. For farming systems which include crops or pasture, minimising the importation of fertiliser nutrients from off-site, and reducing the loss of nutrients from the site, are vital to avoiding environmental impacts and to producing efficiently. This must be achieved while ensuring the supply of the right mix of nutrients at the right time (of year and in terms of conditions) to meet the needs of crops and pastures and using the right application techniques to maximise uptake and minimise waste. A wide range of solutions are available to improve nutrient management, depending on the specifics of the farm. Aspects of nutrient management which are sometimes overlooked include regular soil testing and recognising both the nutrient value and mix of manure and slurry, the deposition of nitrogen from the atmosphere, and the input of nitrogen from legumes when estimating requirements. A thorough audit of on-farm nutrient use and loss can ensure efficient application of additional nutrients.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Nutrient Management	Nutrient balance (NPK)	Calculates farm-gate NPK ratios based on initial data collection sheet information on crop, livestock, & livestock product imports/exports & their associated (generic average) NPK contents. Inputs of N (generic average data) include N fixation, atmospheric inputs & purchased nutrients. Score based on NPK surplus / deficits	The score is based on Guide to Nutrient Budgeting (IOTA 2015)

FIG 19: AVERAGE SCORES FOR THE NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT INDICATOR (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR.

3.2.6. ANIMAL HUSBANDRY

Performance across the indicators for the animal husbandry category was exceptionally high, with minimal variation in scores (Fig 20a). Only 33% of farms do not house their livestock but all farm animals were able to perform natural feeding and social behaviour, and 88% were able to perform natural resting behaviour. While mortality rates varied from below to above average for the group, all had better than average culling rates and low rates of lameness, hair problems and feed disorders, indicating high health and welfare.

As the GFM is developed, we are investigating whether the assessment questions and scoring on animal health and welfare (Fig. 20b) are granular enough and whether they reflect the realities of different livestock systems. One focus for improvements will be to move towards more animal-based indicators, and away from practice-based questions.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Animal Husbandry	Feed input efficiency	The energy value (MJ) of livestock exported for human consumption is calculated from Initial Data collection sheet, as is the energy value (MJ) of feed imported. This is calculated as the edible energy (MJ) fed per unit of human-edible animal product produced (MJ) using data from Wilkinson (2011)	Expert opinion
Animal Husbandry	Management system	Information on access to pasture/range for different species: i) months of access, ii) hours grazing per day in a season, iii) access to outdoor run if not at pasture, then questions on the ability of the animals to perform natural behaviour when feeding, resting and social/comfort, and a question on abnormal behaviour	Expert opinion
Animal Husbandry	Health and welfare	Twenty questions on approaches to vaccination, antibiotic use, anti-parasite treatments and management, mortality and culling rates; longevity of breeding animals, lameness incidence, hair/fleece problems, mastitis incidence (in dairy animals), feed related disorders, conception rates, sanitary status; somatic cell counts (for dairy systems) and performance at the abattoir	Expert opinion

FIG 20: AVERAGE SCORES FOR ANIMAL HUSBANDRY INDICATORS (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR.

3.2.7. CROP AND PLANT HEALTH

The trial group performed well in the plant and crop health category indicators (Fig 21a), with only a small amount of variation between scores. As with animal husbandry, further investigation is needed to determine the extent to which these results reflect the reality of farming practice versus how much is due to the questions asked and scoring method (Fig 21b). The crop rotation indicator exemplifies potential issues. Rotations are associated with resilient crop and pasture production and reducing the number of interventions, such as pesticide and fertiliser application, needed — as a result increasing rotation diversity is scored positively.

However, the score given is strongly affected by the answers to the grassland diversity question. In this trial, 80% of farmers reporting having ‘diverse/highly diverse’ grasslands while only 56% reported having diverse and highly integrated crop systems — and 44% reported minimal rotations in their system. The masking of the relatively low scoring answers for crop rotations by high scores for grassland diversity demonstrates the need to look beneath the surface of headline scores when considering the output of any tool, in order to identify the drivers of the findings and focus attention on the most effective ways to support improvements.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Crop and plant health	Diversity in crop rotation and grassland	Two questions on diversity in the crop rotation and diversity in grassland	Expert opinion
Crop and plant Health	Pesticide use	Average number of spray rounds per crop type	Compared to national figures from DEFRA Pesticide Usage Surveys

FIG 21: AVERAGE SCORES FOR CROP AND PLANT HEALTH INDICATORS (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR.

3.2.8. BIODIVERSITY

Overall, the group had an average score for biodiversity (Fig 22) — performing strongest in natural biodiversity, followed by landscape and agricultural biodiversity. There was a wide range of scores in agricultural and landscape indicators, with less variation in natural biodiversity. The variation in scoring for agricultural biodiversity will in part be due to the differences in farming systems trialled. Arable systems tended to have a higher diversity of crops, with an average of six species and 10 varieties of crop per farm. Livestock farms, on the other hand, had an average of two breeds of animal — with the exception of beef systems, which had an average of 15 breeds.

Variation in farm size will affect the number of breeds it is feasible to have in one system. Most of the farms reported positive practices associated with improved natural biodiversity, as reflected in the high indicator score. However, it is interesting to see some of the practices which are least popular among the trial group. For example, 30% connect habitats on their farm and plant new hedges, 20% have wildflower strips, while only 10% manage their hedgerows to benefit wildlife. Similarly, an average of 8.4% of land is left as un-productive. It is important to understand uptake of practices in the local context — leaving areas of land out of production and planted with wildflowers, for example, may not be appropriate for the local climate or context

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Biodiversity	Planned biodiversity	Score based on average of the number of crop species/varieties present and the number of livestock species/breeds present (an additional variety/breed counted as plus one, and same for an additional species – so not differentiated)	Expert opinion
Biodiversity	Farm habitats and management	Two questions i) which of a list of practices for biodiversity (drawn from Cool Farm Tool list) are carried out, ii) No. of habitats present (habitats from ‘UK Hab’ habitat classification system plus (for arable land) Level 5 habitat classifications including types of <u>margin</u> , iii) % non-productive land	Expert opinion
Biodiversity	Wild biodiversity	Scored based on outcomes (no. of species) of a bird (Big Farmland Bird Count method but only using presence/absence, not highest no. seen) and a butterfly survey (UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme method, through summer)	Expert opinion

FIG 22: AVERAGE SCORES FOR BIODIVERSITY INDICATORS (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR.

3.2.9. SOCIAL

The group had a slightly below average performance in the social category (Fig. 23a). While most improvement could be made in community engagement and farm structure, further consideration could also be given to the highest scoring indicator, social health, in which the range of scores was particularly high.

The relatively low scores largely reflect management practices (Fig. 23b). A third of the trial group sell direct to customers in their local community while in terms of access 60% have public rights of way on their land. Half of the group host occasional walks and workshops, while 40% host educational activities and 15% offer apprenticeships or volunteering opportunities. Again, it is important to emphasise that information should be considered in relation to the local farming context, including the size of the farm, resources available to support community engagement activities, location, etc.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Social	Community	Yes/no questions on whether the farm: i) hosts educational activities, ii) provides apprenticeships and work placements, iii) provides volunteering opportunities. Then questions on the number of activities for local people, means of communication used and the number of visitors to the farm in the year	Expert opinion
Social	Social Health	Whether farm sells produce direct to customers, percent of workers from within ten miles of the farm, level of public access (ranging from none to open access)	Expert opinion
Social	Farm structure	Two questions on legal structure and participation of owners, family, and workers in decision-making	Expert opinion

FIG 23: AVERAGE SCORES FOR SOCIAL INDICATORS (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR.

3.2.10. HUMAN

Scores for the human category and indicators were above average and consistent across the indicators (Fig 24). There was a relatively large range of scores, with some farms achieving maximum scores for the indicators training and capacity building and employment.

Although 70% reported a ‘hard/very hard’ level of work required to run the farm, 40% of respondents manage this by sharing the workload with neighbouring farms. A healthy working environment

is indicated by a low number of sick days — the group recorded an average of 2.8 days per year (with a range from 1 — 10), which sits comfortably below the national average of 4.4. Still, to understand this figure further, more information is needed on the number of workers (including the farmer) coming to work while sick to the detriment of themselves and others. Along with an average of 4.25 training days per year (ranging from 1–8), these results indicate that at least some farmers are adopting practices and creating a working culture likely to support personal and business resilience.

Category	Scores	Contributing questions / data	Basis for scoring
Human	Employment and working hours	No. FT and PT staff (including family members and volunteers) and total number of hours worked in the 12-month period, converted to Full Time Equivalents (240 days/year or 1872 hours) per 100ha	Compared to regional average from Morison et al (2005)
Human	Training & capacity building	Number of training days all staff have had over 12 month period	Training days compared to average training days from Statista.com (2017)
Human	Workforce health and well-being	Eight questions: social activities that involve the staff, such as shared meals, coffee breaks, social media groups, social events, daily/weekly meetings, team-building days etc., the total no. sick days recorded in the 12-month period (converted to % of FTE), remaining questions on working conditions, covering risk assessments, exposure to hazardous chemicals, workload, sharing workload with neighbouring farmers and amount of holiday. Plus, calc of average no. of hours worked per FTE versus the working time directive	Sick days benchmarked versus national average for agric, forestry, and fishing sector for 2017, hours worked compared with Working Time Directive

FIG 24: AVERAGE SCORES FOR HUMAN INDICATORS (A) AND A SUMMARY OF HOW THOSE SCORES ARE CALCULATED (B). VERTICAL LINES (A) INDICATE THE RANGE OF INDIVIDUAL SCORES FOR EACH INDICATOR.

3.3. CONCLUSIONS

The GFM research tool results summarised above at the whole trial level, enable farmers to consider farm sustainability across economic, social, and environmental categories. This provides an overview of strengths and areas for improvement, widens perspectives on what sustainability includes, and as a result should reduce the chances that decisions made on-farm will cause unintended consequences for often overlooked aspects of sustainability.

The group summary and the individual results received by farmers should provide a starting point for farmers to consider ways they might improve their system, including in discussion with their peers, with their workers, with advisors, and with other stakeholders as appropriate. Repeating such an assessment over time can help to track progress and to spot any trade-offs (or 'win-wins') which were not previously recognised.

Limitations of the results have been discussed in preceding sections — it is important for any findings of this type to be the start of processes of reflection, discussion and change, signposting areas to look into further rather than being taken in uncritically. Section 5 considers the feedback from the trial and highlights solutions that could improve this and similar assessments in terms of robustness and usability.

For the Monmouthshire farmers involved in this trial, the best category results (top five) were in animal husbandry, crop and plant health, human, productivity, and soil. The lowest five scoring categories were water, nutrient management, energy and resource use, social, and biodiversity. These five areas may be seen as priorities for improvement, while variation in scores within the group offer opportunities for learning between high and low scoring farms in particular categories. Although each farm is different, meaning that formal benchmarking can be misleading, the informal benchmarking and discussions which take place within a group of farmers can lead to mutual learning and a realistic understanding of the meaning and causes of differences in the results.

3.4. FARMER AND FARM ADVISOR TRIAL FEEDBACK

This section covers the following project activities (Table 1): Collect feedback from farmers undertaking the trial (and the farm advisors supporting them) to examine:

1. How the assessment affected their views on sustainability and the likelihood that they would seek to improve sustainability performance
2. How the process of the trial worked for them, and what might be improved
3. Their feelings about the results and the performance of the assessment tool itself

3.5. APPROACH

Farmer feedback on the trial was collected via a short pre-assessment questionnaire presented online as part of registration to use the online GFM research tool (Appendix B). At the end of the trial, farmers were interviewed by farm advisors using a questionnaire requiring open responses and some multiple-choice answers (Appendix C). The aims of these two approaches were to understand the extent to which the assessment i) altered farmers' perspectives on sustainability, ii) was likely to drive improvements in sustainability and iii) was effective, practical, and viewed as legitimate (robust, trustworthy). Of the eleven farmers who completed the trial, eight filled in the pre-assessment questionnaire, and six were interviewed at the end of the assessment.

The advisors who supported the farmers through the trial were also interviewed after all assessments were completed to ascertain their views of the GFM research tool, their experiences with it and their recommendations for potential improvement. These findings were used to triangulate the feedback provided by farmers (gain multiple perspectives in order to increase confidence in the results) (see Appendix D for the interview question guide). All participants were provided with full information on the nature of the research and informed of their right to refuse to take part, to withdraw at any time, or to ask that their information should not be used after providing it. All data collected were stored anonymously and securely and were anonymised before presentation in this report.

3.6. FINDINGS

3.6.1. OPENING QUESTIONNAIRE

Before the trial, of nine respondents to the multiple-choice questions, seven reported thinking that sustainability was essential to farming, and two that it was important but not essential. Four farmers thought that their on-farm sustainability was 'Fair', four that it was 'Good' and one that it was 'Very good'.

The reasons farmers reported having for joining the trial fell into three groups: i) those who wanted to assess their sustainability performance and/or compare it with that of others, including in order to use the assessment to make improvements on their farm, ii) those who were interested in sustainability and wanted to learn more, and iii) those who wanted to influence the sustainability agenda, either through being active in supporting sustainability research or through getting their voice heard.

This range of reasons, along with the multiple-choice responses, suggests that all the farmers have some awareness of the sustainability agenda and, at least for those in group (i), consider it positively and want to improve. For those in groups (ii) and (iii), critiques of the assessment might be expected to be more general and relate to the direction of travel it might represent for the sector (and the environment) while those with a more farm-performance approach might be expected to view it more in relation to what it says about their farm in particular, and the extent to which it could help them meet their goals.

Definitions of sustainability put forward by farmers focused on production with reduced impacts on the environment, and in one case on the importance of high animal welfare standards. Efficiency and the ability to farm in ways that could be sustained in the long term were highlighted. In terms of the perceived balance between production and the environment, some focused on avoiding harm and depletion, others on minimising the impacts associated with maintaining production and profit. Again, these details are only based on eight responses, but subtle differences in how the balance between nature and production is perceived are visible and likely to lead to different priorities and diverse outcomes between farms and systems.

As other researchers have found, identifying systems and practices that benefit both productivity and the environment is key to enabling transformational changes in farming, as in this case the two goals will not be in competition. Where this is not possible, holistic sustainability assessment across environmental, economic, and social themes will be important in highlighting the extent and importance of trade-offs between different sustainability aims, so that choices are taken in an informed way. This should help avoid unintended consequences where there are multiple trade-offs and more subtle relationships between different impacts — including over the longer term and in relation to off-farm impacts.

Perhaps unsurprisingly (see section 3 on the results of the farm advisor research) none of the farmers emphasized social sustainability in their definitions, likely reflecting the policy and media focus on the environmental impacts of farming and the growing risks associated with climate change.

Farmers went into the trial with a range of ideas about improving sustainability on their farms. For some, the purpose of the assessment was to help them understand what they might do to be more sustainable. For others, the focus was on reducing inputs from off the farm (e.g., feed, fertilizer, fuel) or making changes to increase efficiency in their system. Two respondents wanted to make more systemic changes around their production system and farm environment.

Within such a small group, this range of ambition, perhaps linked to the different ways in which sustainability was viewed by different farmers, reflects the extent to which a sustainability assessment must be applicable to a broad range of contexts and aspirations. This is of particular importance when considering whether, and how, performance should be scored in an assessment to avoid either, discouraging those with conservative ambitions through challenging scoring of performance or, through lenient scoring, reducing the impetus for change among those who want to be more transformative.

3.6.2. END OF TRIAL FARMER INTERVIEWS

Six of the eleven trial farmers took part in an end-of-assessment interview with a farm advisor, and their answers to each question are summarised in Table 9. Although the questionnaire responses are in-depth, given the sample only represents a subset of farming systems in one area of the country, further work would be needed to ensure that the full range of potential benefits and issues with these types of assessment is captured for Wales as a whole.

However, the findings provide a useful insight into the farmers' experience of the trial, and into the benefits and issues associated with the implementation of sustainability assessments in Monmouthshire.

TABLE 9: SUMMARY OF FARMER RESPONSES FROM END-OF-ASSESSMENT INTERVIEWS WITH A FARM ADVISOR.

Question	Response summary (six farmer interviews)
Farmer definitions of sustainability	The definitions of sustainability offered by the farmers focussed on the concept of balance - between inputs and outputs (avoiding waste which pollutes the environment), between the environment and production (including consideration for future generations and their ability to feed themselves), and between the environment and profitability, focussing on the need for economic viability in order for the farm to survive.
Following the assessment, do you feel that sustainability is: essential, important but not essential, Positive but not important, neither positive nor negative, or is negative to good farming practice?	Five farmers said sustainability was essential to farm practice, one said important but not essential. One farmer who said it was essential also said that where we are now, sustainability is treated as if it is important but not essential to good farming practice
What is your view of your farm's level of sustainability now that you've completed the assessment: poor, fair, good or very good or excellent?	Two farmers said their sustainability was fair, three said it was good (one of whom said 'good or very good') and one gave a narrative answer describing how he felt performance was strong in some areas, but in others that they needed advice and ideas on how to improve
Following the assessment do you feel you're much less likely, less likely, neither more nor less likely, more likely or much more likely to improve the sustainability of your farm?	Five farmers said they were more likely to improve the sustainability of their farm, one said they were much more likely. Themes in the comments associated with these answers focussed on how the assessment had caused them to think about sustainability more deeply or more broadly, as well as helping them to see the benefits (e.g., to the farm business) of certain improvements - although the issue of the costs of change and how they limit what farmers could do was raised. In addition, the role of the farm advisor in helping farmers identify options for change and their benefits, as well as a desire to talk to other farmers and gain outside ideas in order to find ways forward were mentioned. For some farmers, pre-existing interests and perspectives - such as a focus on the need to enable future generations to thrive and grow food - as well as an understanding that policy was heading towards support for sustainability, underpinned some farmers' thinking.
Now that you've completed the assessment what new ideas if any, do you have about how you could improve the sustainability of your farm given the resources to do so?	Five out of six farmers had new plans for improving sustainability as a result of completing the assessment. These related either to the environment within which production takes place (hedges, ponds, field margins, headlands) or to farming practices (grazing method, soil management, reducing chemicals and using / diversifying cover crops). There were comments on the lack of recognition for things that farmers do themselves outside schemes (like tree planting) and the need to provide support for those wanting to improve on reasonable practice, beyond giving funding to help those doing badly - which could be seen as rewarding failure. One farmer did not have new plans but said he was already doing a lot of work on sustainability
Could you list any other tools that you currently use to support your decision making, or assessments that you have or aim to complete this year?	Four farmers had used <u>AgreCalc</u> to do carbon footprinting (some via this trial), with other tools used for daily liveweight gain monitoring, IPM / spray records, financial software and nitrogen use. One farmer included soil testing in this answer

How did you find collecting the information needed, very easy, quite easy, neutral, difficult or very difficult?	Three farmers reported that the assessment was fairly or very easy, although in one case the farmer felt that someone less young and confident with technology might have struggled more, while another of these three admitted that if he had needed to do the soil data collection himself it would have been more difficult - but also highlighted the fact that he found it easier because he was able to use information he already had available from entering it into other software. Other comments were that the if the assessment had taken place in winter, it would have been much easier to commit the time required to it, that the tool could have been clearer to enable data to be inputted more straightforwardly. and alluded issues with the questions asked (not all specified)
What if anything would have made gathering data information for the assessment easier?	Farmers focussed on the issue of data requests being very specific (like cost for every different enterprise) while their records were for the whole farm, and whether this level of details was necessary, and about other data (like yearly electricity use) being hard to find. There was a suggestion to align financial data collection with how these data are recorded in farm accounts and having a software link to move data between different platforms/tools. Another theme in responses was that the assessment would be much easier to undertake in the winter, and one farmer emphasised the importance of having the advisor to help them through the assessment and to link it to options for change.
what if anything did you learn about your farm or about sustainability from collecting the data required for the assessment?	Farmers reported having learned about the amount of linear features (hedges, water courses) on their farms, as well as about the state of different aspects of the farm (like the soil); both the amount (potential to make a difference to things) and the revelation of issues (areas for improvement) appeared to focus farmers on thinking about what they could do next, while viewing all aspects of the farm together was also viewed positively
Have you felt any of the information you had to collect was not relevant to sustainability?	Three farmers did not think that any of the information requested was irrelevant to sustainability - one because he recognised the breadth of the term. In contrast another comment questioned whether financial data on sales for one year was relevant, while others felt too much data was asked for in general, and on financial aspects in particular. One respondent highlighted the importance of getting alignment between different assessments/tools on how questions on the same topic were worded and what they asked for, to ensure accuracy in answers
What aspects of your farm sustainability if any did you feel the assessment overlooked?	Three farmers felt that nothing was overlooked in relation to sustainability. Other comments suggested that farmers were not sure if the <u>amount</u> of things like hedges was fully covered and <u>in particular pointed out</u> characteristics that weren't accounted for (like hedge width, gullies around water courses) while it was pointed out that beekeeping was not accounted for, despite its importance
In what ways if any do you think the assessment results could help your farm business?	In terms of the impacts of the assessment on the farm business, one comment focussed on the importance of using the results to anticipate and make the most of future policy support. More practically, farmers felt that impacts would be longer term, especially in terms of their financial choices, including monitoring to see how changes affected yields the following year. Financial benefits were emphasised as well as a perceived balancing required between sustainability and finances. In contrast others focused on efficiency - reducing inputs while improving or maintaining production - or felt that due to input costs, financial benefits and sustainability could go hand in hand but with a balance to be struck between them and yields. Finally, one farmer spoke about the need to take time to think about the results.

In what ways do you think the assessment results could help you to further improve your farming practices?	In terms of changing practices, three farmers had covered this in changes to the business. For the others, barriers to change were referred to here - the costs (workload and monetary), the practicality in relation to on-farm events for more remote, simple systems, and the confidence to run events and farm visits. The need for incentives, especially if sustainability reduced productive land, as with planting new woodlands, was highlighted
Given the opportunity in the future to what extent would you find it useful to repeat this assessment, not at all, slightly, moderately, very useful for extremely useful?	Two farmers thought the assessment would be useful to repeat. two that it would be very useful, one thought it would be moderately useful and one gave a range from moderate to very useful. The positive answers recognised the value of being able to see whether changes made on the farm had improved things, with one response emphasising the value of wider uptake for looking at performance across more farms. A clear message from the farmers was that change takes time, and that an assessment every 2-5 years would make sense in terms of enabling comparisons over time, given that some changes would be slow to filter through.
How well do you feel the results reflected the sustainability for your farm?	Five of the six farmers felt that the assessment was a fair reflection of their farm's sustainability. However, one highlighted the issue that unusual conditions in a given year could produce a false sense of real sustainability, and this was also picked up by a farmer who was positive about the findings but felt that the worm count had been affected by very dry conditions during sampling. Another felt that farm biodiversity had not been fully valued in the assessment, and two farmers reported being uncertain about the reasons for their low scoring in the nutrient management category.
Do you have any other thoughts or comments about sustainability?	Responses included a realisation of the increasing importance of farm sustainability and the need for farmers to face these issues - this was linked to a hope for (or observation of) the movement of policy towards sustainability in Wales, and the need to view this as an opportunity - one farmer highlighted the previous role of agronomists employed by farm suppliers in driving chemical use, and how this was changing as a result of the sustainability agenda, while another expressed a desire to get together with other farmers who had undertaken the assessment to learn from them

The farmer responses described, demonstrated that the farmers involved in the assessment recognised the importance of sustainability. However, most appeared to focus on trade-offs when thinking about sustainability and production, with a subtle difference between those who highlighted the trade-off with production itself, and those who focussed on the trade-off with profit; financial support for improving sustainability would only be likely to affect the latter as a barrier to change. Most (if they were not already undertaking improvements) felt they were more likely to work on their sustainability than they had been before the assessment and felt that the assessment gave them new insights into the sustainability of their farm and how they could improve it. Such improvements related to production-related practices and to the creation of habitat.

In relation to the assessment itself, there was some concern that the extent of improvements they had made to on-farm biodiversity was not taken into account, although this was accompanied by general agreement that the assessment took too long, highlighting the difficult balance to be struck between practicality and robustness. It was clear

that having farm advisors collect data for the farmers had made the process much easier for them, while some recognised that for older and less tech-savvy farmers the process would be likely to be much more challenging.

Overall farmers appeared satisfied with their results and did not feel that too much was overlooked by the assessment, with some issues around the meaning of nutrient management results and the score returned from what was seen as an over-detailed financial category. The need for an alignment of the data requested with the data needed by other software was repeated, along with requests for more intuitive and simple tool design. General comments and details in farmers' responses highlighted the value of a supportive policy context to improving sustainability, and the role of external stakeholders (such as agronomists associated with suppliers) in driving the direction of farming.

3.6.3. END OF TRIAL FARM ADVISOR INTERVIEWS

The analysis of the interview carried out with the two WUF advisors involved in the trial revealed 11 themes (Table 10). The themes linked closely to the design requirements of a good assessment put forward by advisors during the workshop in BUILT Wells, confirming that these aspects of an assessment were important in practice (Fig. 25).

The issues raised by the advisors related to the assessment itself as well as to the wider context of engagement. Those wider issues (represented by the ovals detached from specific aspects of assessment design (Fig. 25)) relate to each other and to the more specific aspects identified (ovals positioned alongside specific assessment characteristics).

The easiest issues to understand are the time taken to complete the assessment, and how this affects the willingness to repeat the assessment. The theme of time taken can be used as the focal point to understand all the themes revealed by the analysis.

At the simplest level, time taken can be addressed by careful assessment design to minimise required data inputs, to maximise the clarity with which such data are requested (including additional information provided within the user interface), and to maximise the simplicity and speed of data collection through straightforward, flexible methods and clear protocols to be followed.

Time taken to complete the assessment can also be addressed through providing support with data collection, data input and instructions (especially for those who struggle with IT). In turn, those providing support will need training.

One reason assessments can take time is when their methods lack robustness (e.g. concerns over soil infiltration testing) or seem irrelevant to the farmer. Aligning assessments with policy and other frameworks helps address this—saving farmers time by reusing data and improving their understanding of what's being asked.

When assessment outcomes are relevant and offer ways to improve the farm system, farmers are more likely to engage. Advisors stressed the need for support to interpret results and access change resources. They also highlighted the power of group approaches—like benchmarking—as a way to motivate improvement through shared learning and peer comparison.

Fig. 25: Mapping of themes raised by advisors based on trial experience (black ovals) onto themes (dark grey) and categories (light grey) relating to the required characteristics of a sustainability assessment put forward by advisors at the farm workshop and onto the solutions put forward to tackle knowledge and cognitive barriers to engaging with farmers on sustainability (white rectangles).

TABLE 10: THEMES DERIVED FROM ANALYSIS OF THE INTERVIEW WITH FARM ADVISORS INVOLVED IN THE TRIAL, INCLUDING EXAMPLE COMMENTS RELATING TO EACH.

Theme title	Theme description	Example comment
Advisor perspective	The advisors reported finding that the process of undertaking the assessment - as well as being challenging (see 'Time taken') - also enabled them to look differently at the whole farm system and to see connections between different aspects and their impact on sustainability. More generally, they highlighted an issue that in some cases agronomists and other advisors close to retirement might be unwilling to explore these types of topics with farmers - and that if their farmers were also close to retirement that feeling was mutual. In contrast, new advisors coming into the sector were much keener to drive change.	It's been absolutely fascinating for me, I've really, really enjoyed it, it's been flipping hard work this last couple of weeks trying to get it all done but yes I think working with these arable famers who are very intensive and very productive and thinking about sustainability in relation to their farms and the comparison to the initial group who volunteered because they were already sustainable, [...] you know using this framework to compare the different models, yes has been really interesting
Alignment	The importance of assessments aligning to current policy messaging and plans for motivating engagement with farmers. In addition, where assessments cover the same topics as an assessment, using the same language and categorisations which farmers have encountered when joining previous government schemes helps them to understand what is being asked and why it is important, speeding up the process. Alignment also helps advisors - current work around the Natural Capital agenda enables them to adjust more easily to the wider scope of a sustainability assessment. Alignment with tools such as carbon footprinting tools was also raised as important to improve, in this case in terms of the scale at which the same data are collected. Finally, there was recognition that changing to a new way of looking at things - in this case towards a holistic view of sustainability - would always involve a big initial effort, until farmers started to understand better what was needed and how everything was going to work.	I'm really glad that the SFS document has been published now because when I'm going back to the farmers with their reports and to sort of wrap up the trial, it is really useful to refer to that and say look this is what we've been doing, this is really valuable for, it will be really valuable this experience while applying for the sustainable farming scheme. <u>Yes</u> I'm sure we'd have got more interest if that had been published before we had that first event
Benchmarking	Farmers can be positively incentivised if they can compare themselves favourably with the performance of other farms and use the information to build on success in this respect	we've gone back to a farmer and said, okay you've got an organic matter level of 3.4 and this is the average across this area, and you can see where you fit within this graph. It's kind of trying to encourage them to see it, okay my organic matters a bit low where I can see there's quite a high percentage of people on double what I've got and enthuse them you know, incentivise them to do more
Trust	Advisors found some concern among farmers about sharing financial data, but not around sharing data on other topics	there was concern about putting in information from your accounts but all other parts of the assessment it was very straight forward really

Design	Issues with how data input is presented and with duplication, as well as difficulties with terminology were highlighted. Replication was spotted in some questions, in others the need to ask the same questions for each enterprise on the farm was raised as important to ensuring the data provided were meaningful. Issues of design also related to methods, with a recognition of trade-offs between using simpler, cheaper tests and the reliability of data collected. The importance of ensuring that data collected were meaningful was raised, with a focus on the soil infiltration test which was found to be very inconsistent and of little value. This can affect willingness to spend time on the assessment. The meaningfulness of data requested was sometimes affected by limits to the scope of the assessment - questions did not cover more marginal production systems (e.g., goats) and did not seem well-adapted to poultry farming. There was a particular issue with questions relating to farm practices in that advisors commented that practice data often need a high level of detail to be useable for other things, such as reporting to government, and also for them to pick up changes in what farmers are doing (e.g., around hedge management). There was a concern that some important practices for the environment (such as the type and maintenance of slurry storage) were not asked about. The design of the engagement process itself was also commented upon, focussing on the need for face-to-face rather than online introductory sessions to allow farmers to ask questions and consider things in their own way, and on the timing of the assessment - farmers and advisors believed that the assessment would have been easier to find time for in the winter, and the advisors felt this could have increased the number of farmers joining the trial	...also the habitat classifications. I found it <u>really difficult</u> to understand [...] To understand what they've got and how to categorise the type of grassland they have It would be valuable I think to know the width of the buffer strips. I suppose this is always just adding complexities it's difficult, we're saying on the one hand you need to simplify it and make it quicker and then suggesting other things that you can add Unless you go out there and purchase you know monitoring equipment, which we're not going to ask farmers to do, it's <u>really hard</u> to kind of measure that infiltration but it's also equally as important. <u>So</u> it's trying to find a method that a farmer can do easily and quickly but also isn't going to cost them a lot of money
Farmer interests	The trial was made up of farmers who were already interested in sustainability, and those persuaded by the advisors in return for carbon footprinting and with the understanding that the advisor would do a lot of the data collection. The former did not show much change in their perspectives as they already had a strong interest	the core group that we started with, the ones that came to the webinar came because they were organic farmers, farmers that were interested in going organic. People that were interested in sustainability and in demonstrating their sustainability
Linking sustainability to economics	The advisors reported that farmers were very positive about the fact that economic sustainability was included and linked to environmental sustainability, and emphasised that they couldn't do anything on sustainability if they weren't viable as a business	...bringing <u>all of</u> these strands of sustainability together and they really get that, they understand <u>that</u> , they like the fact that it's taking account of economic sustainability.

TABLE 10 (CONT.)

Repeating assessment	One farmer just starting out mentioned the potential value to him of repeating the assessment to gauge his progress, and the advisors recognised the potential for using change over time to help farmers see the impacts of changes they made and feel positive about them, there was a strong feeling that farmers would not want to go through the assessment process again due to its length and difficulty	I think most people probably won't do it again to be honest, I think it's been a lot of work to get them through this process, I don't think they'll be keen to go back and embark on it again unless it's massively simplified or unless again there's somebody to help them and push them through the process
Support required	This theme included comments about the need for support for farmers to enable them to complete an assessment that can take many hours, either through advisors actively working on the assessment with them or by offering incentives such as soil testing or a biodiversity survey which are valuable to them for meeting other goals. It also included support for farmers and advisors to enable them to work through the assessment efficiently - this might come in the form of training and/or through information in the tool providing clear explanations of terminology and questions. <u>Finally</u> support is needed in relation to assessment outcomes, ensuring advisors have the right knowledge to interpret them, providing signposting to key information sources and ideas for next steps but also in enabling farmers to come together to work on change through discussion groups.	we always direct them to resources or include information in our reports but I think for a farmer going through this certainly they want to know how they can find out more about identifying butterflies or you know whatever managing hedgerows, so yes good resources, access to good resources We've talked about <u>whether or not</u> we can as a sort of outcome from this project we can encourage farmers to join discussion groups or established discussion groups because that's where the, I think that's just so valuable for farmers and learning from each other and going out onto each other's farms
Time taken	Advisors reported two issues - i) the average amount of time to complete an assessment was 4-5 hours for data collection and 4 hours for data input, which was seen as an unrealistic burden and, ii) the effort was more intense for some groups (older farmers with less IT knowledge) and for some systems (mixed farms with more enterprises to report on). For others with simple systems and good organisation of data, data input might be reduced to a minimum of about 2 hours.	the whole problem or the main problem with this process is just that it takes too long. <u>So</u> anything that can reduce the time for the farmer is important.
Value of process	Advisors felt that the interest of farmers and their thinking were most affected by the process of data collection and input, and less by the outcomes, <u>due to the fact that</u> they did not receive a lot of support in terms of interpreting their results or linking them to practice.	I think there were some that were, I feel like it did interest them, it did get them thinking about things that they hadn't previously thought of it did make them start thinking about the hedgerow management and yes it was good to have that time devoted to thinking about some of these issues, especially knowing particularly the sustainable farming scheme, proposals have come out and now they're going, okay this is what they're looking at, this is what we're going to get paid for. This is the kind of thing we know we've got to get <u>to grips with</u>

3.7. CONCLUSIONS

The most important challenge associated with the GFM assessment from the perspective of farmers and farm advisors, was the time taken to complete it, including how this could particularly disadvantage older farmers, those with fewer IT skills, and those with more complex production systems which increase the amount of data required.

Solutions around the time taken include improved design to minimise data requested and to align required information with that requested by other tools and assessments the farmers undertake, ensuring the clarity of assessment design, carrying out the assessment at less busy periods (for these farmers, winter), providing support for data collection and entry (in the form of advisors or through the use of other people or automated techniques to collect data) and, finally, by ensuring the relevance of the assessment to farmers — this might be through alignment with policy or through actions to improve farmer understanding of why such assessments (and sustainability itself) are important to their practice and to the wider community. While the value of benchmarking over time was recognised by farmers, they emphasised that changes in many of the variables measured would take place relatively slowly, so that re-assessment every 2-5 years would be most likely to demonstrate improvements. This needs consideration, and in the context of time taken farmers might be prepared to spend a bit more time on a less frequent assessment than one they thought they would have to repeat annually.

A second challenge was robustness, with farm advisors highlighting that data collection methods which seem unreliable can undermine the willingness of farmers to persevere with any assessment. The solution for developers is to use the latest research to identify robust indicators and methods of data collection which provide robust results in the simplest way possible. This requires balancing against the need to ensure that the final results are robust and at a level of detail which recognises positive aspects of a farm (e.g., the quality of hedgerows for wildlife, not just their length). Focussing down the amount and level of detail of financial information required is also important in relation to farmer trust as well as the lengthiness of the assessment, which stems from a clarity of aims and the careful identification of key indicators in relation to them.

Positively, both the advisors and the farmers were able to identify insights relating to the sustainability of their farms arising from the assessment, new ideas for change and an increased likelihood that they would make improvements. In addition, the farmers valued sustainability within farming practice (with the caveat that, at least for some, they already understood its importance prior to the assessment).

Considering the views of farmers before and after the assessment, the holistic view of on-farm sustainability appeared to highlight for farmers between production or profit and sustainability. This holistic awareness can be beneficial to change and reduce unintended or unexpected consequences, but the interpretation of results needs to provide pathways to change which include 'win-win' social-economic-environmental changes which demonstrate that the farm business and sustainability are not always in opposition (particularly in the long run). Farmers were very aware of the need to ensure food supply for future generations — in the short term the need for more food can create tensions with sustainability actions that reduce production, but in the long-term food production that can be sustained aligns much more with the need for actions to increase environmental sustainability in particular.

Farmer and advisor feedback showed that providing concrete advice and support to interpret assessment results and them into actions on farm, particularly through collective processes in which farmers learn from each other's experiences, is absolutely key to ensuring that a sustainability assessment has a positive real-world impact, and to helping farmers to see its importance beyond the knowledge that policy is moving towards payments for sustainable farming.

4. Overall conclusions

The Space for Local Production project successfully addressed its four objectives (Table 11), engaging farm advisors and farmers in a trial which explored how sustainability assessments can help tackle barriers to

The work identified a process beginning with the learning role of a holistic sustainability framework (the Global Farm Metric), moving to the subsequent formal assessment of sustainability, and including the vital role of farm advisors in facilitating assessments and supporting farmers in identifying options for change.

All project partners would like to thank the farmers who joined this trial and provided feedback – without their engagement this work would not have been possible.

Key practical challenges for sustainability assessment around the time taken for data collection, the need for design clarity, indicator robustness, and alignment between different farm assessments, delivered important lessons for assessment developers and for policy makers wanting to implement such assessments as part of efforts to improve agricultural sustainability.

This report has presented options for tackling these practical challenges, and highlighted how assessments, while central to monitoring the state of farms across economic, social, and environmental aspects of sustainability, must be considered as part of a carefully thought-out process of change.

This process must be properly resourced, tailored to local conditions, and enable farmers (and other stakeholders who contribute to sustainability issues) to work together to develop and move along pathways to change. Ongoing monitoring and mutual learning in these processes can build resilience and the capacity to adapt to global shocks to supply chains and to climatic conditions.

Objective	Findings
Support farms and land-based production to adapt to climate and economic challenges and develop future agricultural opportunities. Support ecological resilience for community wellbeing	Work with Welsh farm advisors identified barriers to engaging farmers on sustainability topics and how these might be overcome. Advisors discussed how a sustainability assessment could help drive change. This led to an understanding of the use of sustainability assessments in a process of change, rather than as a single action. For many farmers, the use of a holistic conceptual framework which clearly identifies the different aspects of farm sustainability to improve knowledge and understanding, seems vital in breaking down barriers to engagement, driving change in itself, and paving the way for subsequent on-farm assessment. These findings define an effective approach to achieving more sustainable farming and more resilient eco-systems in Monmouthshire and beyond, using a holistic framework for sustainability as a starting point.
Mapping/collation of data, tackling the climate and nature emergency through sustainable food and farming processes	Sustainability data were collected from 11 Monmouthshire farms and the findings highlighted priority aspects for improvement as well as areas of good performance across the group. In addition, six farms were supported in undertaking carbon footprinting using the AgreCalc tool. Farmers received reports from the Wye and Usk Foundation, providing concrete options for changes in practices to improve their sustainability performance
Upskill land based, agricultural and community producers/processors to help develop a vibrant, prosperous, and diverse sustainable food economy	Both farmers and farm advisors reported gaining new insights into on-farm sustainability and developing new ideas for improvements they could make on farm. Farmers already committed to change reported being more likely to carry out changes to improve their farm's sustainability than they had before the trial. Concrete actions for improvement were identified on participating farms

TABLE 11: A SUMMARY OF PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND HOW THE WORK DESCRIBED ADDRESSED THEM.

References

- Bryant, A., & Charmaz, K. (2012). The SAGE Handbook of Grounded Theory. In *The SAGE Handbook of Grounded Theory*. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781848607941>
- Hall, P., Holmes–Ling, P., Stewart, K., & Sheane, R. (2010). A review of existing tools and recommendations for improved emissions accounting and reporting within agriculture and horticulture.
- Jungk, R., & Müllert, N. (1987). *Future Workshops: How to Create Desirable Futures*. Institute for Social Inventions.
- Kipling, R. P., & Becoña, G. (2019). Applying a conceptual framework for effective implementation of on–farm greenhouse gas mitigation: Evaluation of knowledge exchange methods in Wales and Uruguay. *Landbauforschung / Journal of Sustainable Organic Agricultural Systems*, 69(1), 13–24. <https://doi.org/10.3220/LBF1581687621000>
- Kipling, R. P., & Özkan Gülzari, Ş. (2016). Stakeholder engagement and the perceptions of researchers: how agricultural modellers view challenges to communication. *Advances in Animal Biosciences*, 7(3), 240–241. <https://doi.org/DOI: 10.1017/S2040470016000273>
- Kipling, R. P., Taft, H. E., Chadwick, D. R., Styles, D., & Moorby, J. (2019a). Challenges to implementing greenhouse gas mitigation measures in livestock agriculture: A conceptual framework for policymakers. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 92, 107–115. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.11.013>
- Kipling, R. P., Taft, H. E., Chadwick, D. R., Styles, D., & Moorby, J. (2019b). Implementation solutions for greenhouse gas mitigation measures in livestock agriculture: A framework for coherent strategy. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 101, 232–244. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.08.015>
- Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., McNaughton Nicholls, C., & Ormston, R. (Eds.). (2014). *Qualitative Research Practice: A Guide for Social Science Students and Researchers* (2nd ed.). SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Taft, H. E., Chadwick, D., Styles, D., Kipling, R. P., & Moorby, J. (2018). Development of a farm–level greenhouse gas emission assessment tool for Welsh livestock agriculture . In C. Heidecke, H. Montgomery, H. Stalb, & L. Wollenberg (Eds.), *International Conference on Agricultural GHG Emissions and Food Security – Connecting research to policy and practice* (p. 35). Thünen.
- Whittaker, C., McManus, M. C., & Smith, P. (2013). A comparison of carbon accounting tools for arable crops in the United Kingdom. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 46, 228–239. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2013.03.015>

Appendix A

Questionnaire sent out to farm advisors in Wales.

Notes: This questionnaire was presented in Google forms in Welsh and English and accessed by participants via a link in an email from Farming Connect inviting them to take part. A pilot version was shared with three experienced farm advisors for feedback and adjusted to improve clarity and ease of response.

SECTION 1 OF 7

Farm advisors and sustainability

We're asking you to fill out the questionnaire below to help us explore your views and needs when engaging with farmers on sustainability. The aim is to help develop support for farmer engagement and knowledge exchange on these topics.

SECTION 2 OF 7

Permissions

I give permission for my questionnaire answers to be used to inform research into farm sustainability knowledge exchange, and to improve the Global Farm Metric sustainability assessment within the Space for Local Production Project, and for these uses only. I understand that:

1) My answers will only be used anonymously, will be kept securely, and will not be stored beyond the requirements of this specific research activity, 2) I have the right to withdraw permission for the use of my answers, by emailing lee.price@menterabusnes.co.uk within 7 days of filling out this questionnaire, 3) I have the right not to answer any questions I do not wish to.

Are you happy to fill in this questionnaire on the terms described above?

*Yes/No

SECTION 3 OF 7

On-farm sustainability

Q1 How would you define sustainability in relation to farming?

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

Q2 For the farmers you interact with, is environmental sustainability currently (please check the answer you agree with most):

Always central to farming practice

On most farms central to farming practice

On some farms central to farming practice

On a few farms central to farming practice

On no farms central to farming practice

Q3 From your answer to Q2, why do you think environmental sustainability is/is not currently central to farming practice?

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

Q4 Do you feel that environmental sustainability is (please check the answer you agree with most):

Negative for good farming practice

Neither positive or negative for good farming practice

Positive but not important for good farming practice

Important but not essential to good farming practice

Essential to good farming practice

Q5 Please give the main reasons for your answer to Q4 on the importance of environmental sustainability to good farming practice

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

SECTION 4 OF 7

Engaging on environmental sustainability

Q6 Do you currently provide information to/advise farmers on any of the topics listed below? (tick all that apply)

Biodiversity

Crop variety or livestock breed resilience and diversity

Soil health

Water management

Air pollution

Greenhouse gas emissions

Energy and resource use

Nutrient management

Plant and crop health

Q7 Would you / do you find it easy to talk about improving environmental sustainability with (check the most relevant single statement):

All of the farmers you engage with

Most of the farmers you engage with

Some of the farmers you engage with

Just a few of the farmers you engage with

None of the farmers you engage with

Q8 Please explain your view (Q7) on whether it is easy to talk to your farmers about environmental sustainability

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

Q9 What main challenges do you think you would have (or have you had) when trying to talk to farmers about environmental sustainability?

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

SECTION 5 OF 7

In the 2nd half of the questionnaire, we focus on social sustainability. This relates to the benefits and impacts of a farm on the local community (e.g., education, access, events, direct sales, engagement) and on its workers (e.g., pay, conditions, safety, equal opportunities) including through its business structure (e.g., involvement of community or workers in planning and decisions)

Q10 For the farmers you interact with, is social sustainability currently (please check the answer you agree with most):

Always central to farming practice

On most farms central to farming practice

On some farms central to farming practice

On a few farms central to farming practice

On no farms central to farming practice

Q11 From your answer to Q10, why do you think social sustainability is/is not currently central to farming practice?

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

Q12 Do you feel that social sustainability is (please check the answer you agree with most):

Negative for good farming practice

Neither positive or negative for good farming practice

Positive but not important for good farming practice

Important but not essential to good farming practice

Essential to good farming practice

Q13 Please give the main reasons for your answer to Q12 on the importance of social sustainability to good farming practice

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

SECTION 6 OF 7

Engaging on social sustainability

Q14 Do you currently provide information to/advise farmers on any of the topics listed below? (check all that apply)

Public access and public health benefits (e.g., from access to the countryside)

Community engagement (visits, education etc.)

Farm structure (ownership and business models)

Health and wellbeing of workers

Training and capacity building for workers

Employment conditions and employee diversity

Sharing skills / experiences with other farmers

Q15 Would you / do you find it easy to talk about improving social sustainability with (check the most relevant single statement):

All of the farmers you engage with

Most of the farmers you engage with

Some of the farmers you engage with

Just a few of the farmers you engage with

None of the farmers you engage with

Q16 Please explain your view (Q15) on whether it is easy to talk to your farmers about social sustainability

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

Q17 What main challenges do you think you would have (or have you had) when trying to talk to farmers about social sustainability?

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

Q18 Do you think the challenges of engaging with farmers on environmental or social sustainability are/would be different from the challenges to engaging them on farm economics or productivity?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Unsure

Q19 Could you give the main reasons for your answer to Q18?

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

SECTION 7 OF 7

And finally, just a couple of questions about you
Q20 For how long have you been a farm advisor or adviser?

OPEN TEXT RESPONSE

Q21 Which of these types of farming system do you work with? (please check as many answers as you like)

Dairy

Sheep

Beef

Mixed (arable and livestock)

Arable

Horticulture

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